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Computer-aided design and experimental evaluation of a novel nucleosome binder

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Robert Giessmann
Frankfurter Straße 5
35037 Marburg

rgiessmann@gmail.com

geboren am 23.08.1990, Berlin

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Erstgutachter: Frau Jun.-Prof. Dr. Olalla Vázquez

Zweitgutachter: Herr Dr. Peter Kolb

Wohin warst du aufgebrochen?

Danksagung

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1. Introduction

1.1. Biological function of nucleosomes

Traditional idea about nucleosome function: compaction of DNA. In contrast to prokaryotes, which store their DNA in the cytoplasm, eukaryotic cells compact their DNA into a specific compartment, the nucleus. The compaction of DNA into nucleosomes, necessary to reach this high level of compaction, is one of the main functions of histone proteins, a family of proteins that is highly conserved between species and strongly alkaline. This compartmentalization allows the separation of nuclear and cytosolic enzymes, a “feature that is crucial for proper functioning of eukaryotic cells”^[1].

Co-functionalities of nucleosomes: a building block for epigenetics. The nucleosome platform allowed further for the development of another layer of gene regulation (besides DNA methylation, which is present also in prokaryotes): the “histone language”. Modifications of the histone proteins influence compaction, and therefore accessibility, of specific genes. This leads to observably different chromatin states, euchromatin and heterochromatin, which are lightly or densely packed, respectively. Finally, during cell division, even denser packed chromosomes are formed.

1.2. Molecular structure of the NCP

General structure of the NCP: histone octamer + DNA. The basic building block of nucleosomes is the so-called nucleosome core particle (NCP). The NCP consists of eight histone proteins, which assemble in a specific manner, and approximately 147 bp of DNA, which are wound around the histone core (for illustration, cf. Figure 1).

Histone proteins consist of a globular core and histone tails. Histone proteins consist of globular core domains, which are brought into close contact within the NCP, and histone tails, which extrude from the NCP. Especially on the outside, the histone octamer (HO) consists to a higher-than-average ratio of positively charged amino acids, which allow to contact and neutralize the highly negatively charged DNA directly.

DNA is wound on the HO in a specific way, leading to nucleosomal supergrooves. DNA bound to histone octamers is undergoing a strong bend, since the DNA helix is turned ~ 1.67 times around the histone octamer into a left-handed super-helix conformation. This leads to formation of so-called “supergrooves”, which consist of DNA minor or major grooves lying parallel on two different gyres of the nucleosomal DNA (for illustration, cf. Figure 2).

Figure 1: **Organization of DNA in eukaryotic cells.** A) The chromosome represents the densest form of DNA during the cell cycle, and is only observable during cell division. B) Heterochromatin is the form present for silenced genes, and is very densely packed. C) The euchromatin-like “beads on a string” form can be visualized with cryo-electron microscopy after induced unpacking as one of the loosest, yet connected forms of nucleosomes. A helical stretch of DNA (D) in B-DNA form, when not bound to histone octamers (E). A histone octamer consists of two molecules of each histone proteins (H2a, H2b, H3, H4). Note that scales differ strongly between the shown structures. From: reference [1].

Figure 2: **Structure of the nucleosome core particle.** A) The nucleosome core particle is presented in a top-view, showing the histone octamer core, and the DNA wound around it. B) In a side view it becomes clear that the DNA minor and major grooves align in a parallel manner, forming “nucleosomal supergrooves” (a supergroove consisting of two minor grooves is marked with red asterisks). The working group of Dervan coined that term in 2004. From: reference [2], pdb id: 1aoi.

1.3. Nucleosomal DNA – a challenging structural target

In detail: nucleosomal DNA possesses unique structure – should allow selective binding. The structure of nucleosomal DNA and its interaction with the histone core was the point of interest of many studies examining the crystal structure of NCPs.^[3–6] Especially the influence of sequence on the structure and stability of the NCP was researched intensively.^[7–9] A series of strong kinks and stretches contributes further to the unique structure of nucleosomal DNA, differing strongly from the structure of linear B-DNA.^[6] Finally, the nucleosomal supergroove brings two DNA minor grooves into close contact, which should allow selective targeting of the nucleosomal DNA.^[10]

1.3.1. Small molecule B-DNA minor groove binders

Small molecule DNA minor groove binders possess similar characteristics. DNA minor groove binders may be structurally diverse, but they often share similar properties, like positive charge (allowing to interact with the negatively charged phosphate groups), unfused heterocycles (allowing the binder to become isohelical with the minor groove), or some ability to participate in hydrogen bonds.^[11] Some of the most popular ones (a list of which is given in Table 1, and more are found in an extensive review^[12]) are used for nucleus staining in fluorescence microscopy. Due to their binding to DNA they are, however, often also toxic or mutagenic (as their presence hinders normal progress of DNA transcription or replication), and may be used as antimicrobials.

Table 1: Popular DNA minor groove binders. Hoechst 33258 and DAPI are used for fluorescence staining, whereas pentamidine is an antimicrobial agent.

Name	Chemical type	PDB id
Hoechst 33258	bisbenzimidazole	264d
DAPI	diamidinophenylindole	1d30
Pentamidine	dicarbamimidoylphenole	1d64

Minor groove binders are usually A/T selective. Pentamidine is A/T selective,^[13] i.e. it prefers the narrow A:T/T:A minor groove over the wider G:C/C:G minor groove. The protruding G-NH₂ group

is steric demanding and acts furthermore as a hydrogen donor, which would have to be accepted by the DNA binders.

G/C binders are underrepresented. Whereas A/T selective minor groove binders are easier to achieve, G/C selective DNA minor groove binders are often more challenging (for a discussion, cf. ref [14]). Examples for G/C selective minor groove binders with fluorescent properties are the antibiotics chromomycin A3 and mithramycin.^[15] However, their carbohydrate moieties are often hard to install in a stereospecific manner, and indicate therefore a rather low synthetic accessibility. Indeed, their prices are high and chromomycin A3 is usually produced in engineered bacteria,^[16] as is mithramycin.^[17]

BAPPA derivatives present a class of tunable DNA minor groove binders with high synthetic accessibility. As presented, a major challenge in the production of DNA minor groove binders is the tuning of their properties. Often, a change in structure leads to change in affinity as well as in the fluorescent properties. Furthermore, synthetic routes were not necessarily designed for easy derivatization of the target molecules.

BAPPA derivatives (e.g. PyBAPPA and PheBAPPA) present a class of tunable, synthetically facile DNA minor groove binders with fluorescent properties, structurally derived from pentamidine.^[18] A route published by Sánchez et al. in 2012 presented an one-pot, combinatorial route to generate multiple derivatives.^[19] The BAPPA moiety can be considered adapted from the pentamidine, or propamidine (a pentamidine derivative), structure (cf. Appendix).

Scheme 1: Chemical structure of PheBAPPA (1) and PyBAPPA (2). Resonance structures of the planar amidinium groups are omitted for clarity. Structures of pentamidine, propamidine, and BAPPA can be found in the Appendix.

1.3.2. Nucleosomal DNA-specific binders

A specific binder for nucleosomal DNA should have a high affinity to the unique features of nucleosomal DNA.

Natural occurring nucleosomal DNA-specific binders. Examples of nucleosomal DNA-specific binders from nature are rare (at least on the current state of knowledge). One example from literature is the chromatin factor RCC1.^[20] However, RCC1 interacts not only with the nucleosomal DNA, but mainly with the histones (contributing 23% and 77% of the interaction, respectively). RCC1 contacts the phosphate backbone and acts therefore sequence-unspecific. The most famous example is probably the dimeric glucocorticoid receptor.^[21] The two monomers contact neighboring major grooves of the nucleosomal DNA with a zinc finger domain, and undertake with a second domain protein-protein interactions.^[22]

A synthetic nucleosomal DNA-specific binder: the nucleosomal supergroove hairpin clamp. To the best of my knowledge, there is only one example in literature of a nucleosomal DNA-specific synthetic binder. In contrast to the glucocorticoid receptor, this binder targets a supergroove consisting of two *minor* grooves lying parallel on the nucleosome. To achieve this, a hairpin pyrrole-imidazole polyamide dimer was developed by the working group of Dervan.^[2] The targeted stretches of DNA were located on outward-facing minor grooves (specifically, nt positions ± 44 to ± 39 , corresponding to the sequences AGTGTA and its complementary, TACACT, in the human α -satellite DNA). However, the recognition mechanism is not only based on the specific structure of nucleosomal DNA (although, formally, the nucleosomal supergroove formed by two gyres of DNA was recognized, a condition that would not occur in dissolved B-DNA), but the high affinity of the ligand was primarily accomplished by recognizing the underlying nucleotide sequence. This hinders clearly the applicability of this construct in NCPs other than the one employed in this study, not to speak of nucleosomes *in vivo*.

1.4. Analysis of DNA-ligand interactions

Understanding the molecular level of DNA-ligand interaction is a prerequisite to rational design. Furthermore, the strength of interaction has to be determined quantitatively to compare different constructs.

1.4.1. *Molecular modelling as a computational tool for analysis of DNA-ligand interactions*

In general: molecular modelling is capable of generating valuable information. In principle, molecular modelling qualifies as a supreme tool to examine interactions in the context of this work. Structures of *receptor* (i.e. nucleosomal DNA) and *ligand* (i.e. DNA minor groove binders) are known, and experimental data on affinities is available. With computational approaches it should therefore be possible to simulate the reciprocal molecular recognition process and to determine *poses* of the ligand, i.e. tentative *binding modes* of the ligand (with binding mode I mean a specific conformation of the ligand at a specific position on the receptor). A *scoring function* then predicts the binding affinity, and can be (within certain limits) correlated to the experimentally accessible interaction strength.

Approaches to analyze DNA-binder interactions in linear DNA: examples from the literature.

To predict DNA-ligand interactions with molecular modelling presents a challenging task for current methods. Srivastava et al. compared multiple docking methods to model DNA minor groove binders.^[23] The examined algorithms were often able to predict the correct pose of the ligand within the poses ranked best by the scoring function, but correlating the scores to experimental data was problematic ($R^2 = 0.26-0.74$).

Another approach is “in silico footprinting”, a technique where molecular dynamics simulations are used to generate an energy profile of a small molecule pulled through the minor groove of a DNA strand.^[24] Although conducted *in vacuo*, the authors could present single time-steps in the generated trajectories which represented favorable binding sites (as known from experimental evidence) and did indeed show small potential energies. However, the authors did not provide an approach to a scoring function, but rather chose to analyze the potential energies qualitatively.

1.4.2. *Footprinting as an experimental tool for analysis of DNA-ligand interactions*

To analyze the interaction of DNA with small molecules, a variety of experimental methods exist, each capitalizing on a different aspect of DNA-ligand binding. The affinity of a specific molecule for a DNA of a given sequence is determined by means of measuring the dissociation constant K_D . Examining interactions of the same ligand with different DNA sequences, the sequence-specificity (or: “sequence-selectivity”) of the ligand is determined. To describe the sequence-selectivity completely, all K_D values for different DNA sequences would have to be given (a daunting task, considering that there are already 136 combinations of four nucleotides in a row). Therefore, it is

more often tried to correlate the K_D with the type of nucleotides in the sequence (A/T or G/C), and to describe recognized patterns (e.g. “A/T selective”, “tolerating G”, etc.).

In general: footprinting is a way to map interactions of DNA binders to their location of effect.

Footprinting is a method to map interactions of any kind to DNA (or RNA) strands. To visualize “footprints” of the interaction, the nucleotide strands are labelled selectively at one end, and then cleaved randomly in a way that each starting molecule of DNA is cleaved once at maximum. The condition of one cleavage per molecule is called “single-hit kinetics”. If an interacting agent, e.g. a DNA minor groove binder, is present at a specific position, the probability of cleavage is reduced at this site (for illustration, cf. Figure 3). Visualizing each labelled fragment of varying length, it is possible to see “footprints” of the interacting agent.

Figure 3: Scheme of the footprinting process. A) Labeled DNA is cleaved randomly. The label is represented by a green signaling attachment, dotted lines indicate randomly distributed potential cleavage sites. B) Cleavage occurred at random positions, but was conducted at conditions that result in a maximum of one cleavage per molecule. Only the black fragment will be visualized. C) An interacting agent, e.g. a DNA minor groove binder (visualized as an orange ellipse), is hampering cleavage at its site of binding.

Footprinting of linear DNA: examples from the literature. To be able to detect minute amounts of DNA fragments, DNA is usually radioactively end-labelled with ^{32}P at one (usually the 3'-end) or both (for palindromic DNA sequences) ends. After separation of fragments by native polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (so-called “sequencing gels”), so-called storage phosphor screens allow to collect signal from the radioactive decay of ^{32}P , and convert it to an image, visualizing the occurrence of fragments of varying length.

Linear B-DNA was used to determine sequence-selectivities of some small molecules, e.g. by using systematic footprinting substrates which contain all possible tetranucleotides,^[25] or all symmetric hexanucleotides.^[26]

Footprinting of nucleosomal DNA: examples from the literature. Footprinting of nucleosomal DNA is known in the literature as well. Two major motivations to footprint nucleosomal DNA can be identified: i) identification of histone-DNA interaction ii) interaction of third parties with histone octamer-bound (i.e. nucleosomal) DNA.

Histone-DNA interactions were analyzed from the very beginning of NCP research, due to the possibility to study accessibility and therefore interaction of DNA with histone proteins. An example presents the case of the development of an artificial strong positioning sequence by the working group of J. Widom, where footprinting of the generated sequence was used to determine the actual binding positions of their DNA substrates.^[9]

Studies on nucleosomal DNA were also conducted for determination of nucleosome-specific alkylation patterns of a potential anti-cancer agent, based on an intercalator moiety,^[27] respectively a platinum analogue of it,^[28] or by natural products.^[29] Also, the building blocks of the aforementioned hairpin PA dimer were footprinted on nucleosomal DNA, to determine the optimal combinations of selective and strong binders.^[30] Furthermore, oxidative charge transport through DNA by a rhodium complex was monitored.^[31]

Capillary electrophoresis: a way to analyze footprinting without the need for radioactivity.

Traditional footprinting includes the use of radioactive isotopes, typically ³²P. Due to recent regulation demanding the substitution of harmful substances with less harmful ones,^[32] the end-labelling with fluorophores (fluorescent dyes coupled to nucleotides, usually attached specifically at the 5'-end) might become more popular. Fluorescent end-labelling allows for handling of samples according to normal laboratory regulation (no shielding from radioisotopes needed) and long-term storage (no decay of radioisotopes), which is a big advantage over radiolabeling.

To increase sensitivity of fluorescence footprinting, it is possible to employ capillary electrophoresis instead of running long sequencing gel. The working principle is the same, but instead of letting the sample run through a wide and thick gel slab, a capillary filled with polymer solution is used. A small window in the capillary is lit by a laser, and the fluorescence emission recorded. By

employment of different fluorophores it is even possible to multiplex samples, i.e. recording independent samples within the same run. Additionally, this allows for including internal size standards, which can be used to align multiple runs accurately.

Examples from literature for successful footprinting with this method include the mapping of promoters from RNA or the identification of protein binding sites on DNA via fluorescently labeled oligonucleotide extension, employing an elongation approach rather than the cleavage produced by DNase I or hydroxyl radicals.^[33] Sequence and/or location of gene regulation sites were determined successfully in multiple cases.^[34–37]

A solid phase-immobilization approach was employed to ease the purification steps when determining binding sites,^[38] and the sensitivity and price efficiency compared to radioactive labelling was found to be sufficient,^[33,37] especially when employing universal primers and a single-reaction, nested PCR approach.^[39]

One of the most advanced approaches is the development of a 96-well assay for DNase I footprinting, enabling high-throughput analysis of ligand binding to specific DNA sequences.^[40] However, to the best of my knowledge, there is no example of analyzing interactions of small molecules with DNA by capillary electrophoresis.

2. Vision and aim

We envision a molecule that is capable of sensing nucleosomal DNA.¹

To achieve this, we want to employ BAPPA derivatives as binding sensor moieties, as they are known to increase their fluorescence intensity upon binding. To increase the magnitude of this light-up effect and to generate selectivity for nucleosomal DNA over free DNA, we want to construct a multivalent ligand. Its multivalency is to be achieved by connecting several binding moieties with a linker scaffold.

In this work, by means of molecular modelling and DNA footprinting, I want to answer the question where basic building blocks of the envisioned multivalent ligand interact favorably with the nucleosomal DNA. Information on favored binding positions and the respective pose of the binding moieties will allow me to predict an optimal structure of such a multivalent ligand.

¹ With *sensing* we mean the signaling of successful binding, which is achieved here *via* increase in fluorescence of the sensor upon binding.

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. Evaluation of the competitive binding of the histone octamer and small ligands to the Widom 601 DNA sequence to determine probable interaction sites

From the available data on binding of histone octamer and small ligands to the strong positioning sequence “Widom 601” it should be possible to derive favorable interaction sites by simple comparison. This is undertaken in this chapter.

3.1.1. *The ligand–DNA interaction is characterized by the ligand's sequence selectivity*

We have to assume that our knowledge of sequences interacting with BAPPA derivatives, namely PheBAPPA and PyBAPPA, is not complete, as – to the best of my knowledge – not all possible tetranucleotide sequences were tested yet.

Assuming that our knowledge of the mentioned BAPPA derivatives' favored sequences is nevertheless enough to predict all of the most likely binding sites in DNA (as binding affinities decrease strongly with less optimal sequences), I developed a small script finding the known subsequences (namely: AAATTT, AATTT, AATT, AAGTT, AGATT, AAGCTT, and GGCCC, taken from Sánchez et al.^[19]) or their reverse and/or complementary equivalents with a determined dissociation constant (in the case of GGCCC: ∞) in an arbitrary sequence.

This led to the identification of the following possible interaction sites in the Widom 601 DNA (numbering according to Chua et al.^[41]): -64 to -60 (GGCCC), -45 to -42 (AATT), -17 to -13 (AATTT, including AATT), and +13 to +17 (AATTT).²

3.1.2. *The histone–DNA interaction influences binding probabilities*

Considering the NCP in its elements, histone octamer and DNA, it seems intuitive that DNA minor groove binding cannot occur where the DNA is already occupied by the histone octamer.³ The

² Note that, interestingly, in the human α -satellite DNA, the strongest positioning sequence known before the Widom 601 sequence, none of these subsequences could be identified.

³ There are two factors that counter this argument: i) DNA rotation induced by ligand binding, i.e. turning of inward-facing minor grooves to the solvent upon binding by ligands (shown by Brown and Fox^[42]); ii) so-called nucleosome breathing, i.e. constant dissociation and reassociation of the DNA with the histone octamer, leading to time windows in which originally inward-facing minor grooves are accessible (for more details, the reader is referred to a review^[43] by the mother of nucleosome structures, K. Luger).

Figure 5: **3-D structures of possible binding sites.** Crossed-eye stereo views created from pdb id 3lz1, and data from groover. Note to the reader: it is possible to get a visual 3-D impression by crossing your eyes. **A)** Nucleosomal DNA in a side-view. **B)** Nucleosomal DNA and minor groove grid in top-view. **C)** Minor groove grid, in isolated top-view. Nucleotides that correspond to a known interacting sequence are shown in red. The DNA minor groove spheres at those positions are painted red. The DNA minor grooves are to the most part not outward-facing, and are thus predicted to be of low accessibility to externally added binders.

This uncertainty motivates my research to explore the implications and probability of BAPPA derivative binding to nucleosomal DNA. I approached this question in computational and experimental ways to develop a model able to make predictions, which then could be checked against experimental data.

3.2. Exploration of docking tools for simulation of DNA minor groove binding

As presented in the Introduction (Chapter 1.4.1), there are literature-known approaches towards ligand-receptor docking.

However, all of these were considered unsuitable for this project: MD-driven interaction profiling would fail upon the blocked minor groove at the interaction sites with histone proteins (which occurs approximately every 10 bp), as the molecule would not be able to cross this barrier. Furthermore, the bent nature of nucleosomal DNA would complicate the protocol – the attractive force center would have to be moved constantly in very short advance of the ligand to keep the ligand in the minor groove, instead of pulling it unwantedly into the solvent.

Similarly, flexible-ligand docking seemed unsuitable for our aim, as every position would have to be visited by the docking protocol separately, and poses generated multiple times by docking to a position nearby would have to be removed from the results laboriously to generate a uniformly composed data set.

3.2.1. Model evaluation by comparison of computational and experimental data

When using computational models, it is necessary to check their reliability against experimental data. This is done in the following sections for two different docking methods, *AutoDock Vina* and the self-developed *groover-szybki* approach. Analogously, both approaches are first checked for their ability to regenerate a known reference structure. Subsequently, the correlation between experimental determined affinities and the scores calculated by the two approaches is examined to evaluate the predictive strength of the underlying model.

3.2.1.1. Redocking of PheBAPPA to Dickerson DNA with AutoDock Vina

Redocking means the (i) designation of known structure as reference structure, containing receptor (in this case: DNA) and ligand (in this case: minor groove binder), (ii) removal of the ligand from the

structure, (iii) docking of the ligand to the so-generated, ligand-less structure. The results of the docking step are then compared to the known reference structure, and checked for plausibility.

The only structure available on DNA-bound BAPPA is an unpublished NMR structure of PheBAPPA **1** with “Dickerson DNA” from Mateo I. Sánchez. This structure was chosen to be our reference structure and it was proceeded like explained above.

A redocking with *AutoDock Vina* to this dodecamer-DNA generated nine possible ligand poses, scoring each of them with an energy value (for details on the working principle, the reader is referred to the publication introducing *AutoDock Vina* to the scientific community^[44]).

To be able to compare the redocked poses to the reference structure, a local search was performed first. A local search optimizes the ligand in the reference structure with the force field used for docking, so a direct comparison becomes possible.⁵ The score of the optimized ligand and its RMSD to the original reference structure is given in Table 2.

Table 3 gives the RMSD values of the 9 poses scored best (in the following called “Best-9”) by *AutoDock Vina*, including the root mean square deviation (RMSD) to the optimized reference structure. The RMSD value is an indicator of structural similarity, and was here determined for the heavy atoms only. The score of the Best-9 poses is given as well.

As PheBAPPA is a symmetric molecule,⁶ this has to be accounted for when determining the RMSD – if a symmetric molecule with uniquely defined atom names is placed on itself in a flipped manner, atoms at the very ends might be compared to each other due to the algorithm underlying RMSD determination. This flipping leads then to extremely high RMSD values, although the structures are in reality chemically similar (only the virtual atom numbering differs). The order of magnitude for this effect is 11 Å for PheBAPPA (cf. Table 3). To correct this, the structure in question can be compared to reference structures containing both possible orientations, i.e. having different virtual atom numbers. When generating RMSD values by comparison to both symmetric structures, the lower RMSD is the symmetry-corrected one. This effect is widely known and is addressed *AutoDock Vina*-internal,^[44] but not in *Chimera*, the program used by me for determination of RMSD values.

⁵ This is because the force field employed might score the experimentally determined reference structure bad because of its imperfection to resemble reality. A prior optimization of the reference structure with the employed force field reduces this effect.

⁶ Its chemical structure is formally symmetrical. However, when examining the NMR structure of PheBAPPA and the docking results that are following, it becomes clear that BAPPA derivatives bound to DNA rotate the Ar-CH₂-NH-Ar bonds to become more isohelic with their substrate.

Table 2: **Results of reference structure preparation with AutoDock Vina.** The original reference structure (an unpublished NMR structure of PheBAPPA bound to Dickerson DNA, provided by Mateo. I. Sánchez) is optimized by a “local search” of AutoDock Vina. Given are the RMSD values comparing the optimized to the original ligand in two orientations (accounting for the symmetrical Dickerson DNA), and the resulting score.

	RMSD _{A, orig} / Å	RMSD _{B, orig} / Å	Score / kcal mol ⁻¹
optimized reference, orientation A	0.352	-	-7.3
optimized reference, orientation B	-	0.747	-7.6

Table 3: **Results of PheBAPPA redocking to Dickerson DNA by AutoDock Vina.** RMSD values are given for all Best-9 poses against optimized reference structures (“A, opt” and “B, opt” for optimized reference structures in the corresponding orientation; cf. Table 2), respectively. Symmetry-corrected RMSD values are marked in bold. RMSD between “A, opt” and “B, opt” is 11.377 Å.

Best-x pose	RMSD _{A, opt} / Å	RMSD _{B, opt} / Å	Score / kcal mol ⁻¹
1	3.148	11.050	-9.2
2	10.82	1.447	-9.0
3	11.868	3.130	-9.0
4	4.752	12.13	-8.9
5	12.01	2.363	-8.7
6	11.384	3.492	-8.7
7	2.305	11.706	-8.6
8	15.208	11.681	-8.6
9	13.064	6.228	-8.6

Evaluating the Best-9, most of them are within close vicinity of the reference structure. Pose “Best-2” (meaning the pose ranked second best) is closest (1.447 Å), and is also very well ranked. It is interesting to note that the scores of the newly docked poses are better than for the optimized reference structure, probably reflecting the imperfection of the used force field.⁷

The reference structure is usually considered reconstructed, when the RMSD lies within a tolerable range between 1.5–2.5 Å – this condition is not fulfilled for the best pose, but at least for pose “Best-2”. The redocking can thus be considered tentative successful.

3.2.1.2. Correlation of AutoDock Vina scores with experimentally determined K_D values

To evaluate the redocking not only qualitatively, but quantitatively, available data on the dissociation constants (K_D) of BAPPA derivatives binding to different DNA sequences were used to compare them with the scores calculated by AutoDock Vina for docking of PheBAPPA 1 and PyBAPPA 2 to B-DNA models of sequences known to support interactions between BAPPA derivatives and DNA (a list of which is given in Table 4). This allows to determine the quality of our model in regard to describing the experimental data.

In the previous redocking experiment it became clear that *AutoDock Vina* might rank poses best which are not correlating to the experimentally determined most likely binding mode. To reduce this uncertain influence, I decided to employ a multipose binding calculation model, taking into account a thermodynamic view on binding.^[45] Therefore, not only the “Best-1” pose is considered, but rather the whole set of "good" poses, all of which are contributing to binding.⁸ As the *AutoDock Vina* score performed reasonably well for describing the experimentally determined free binding energy ΔG for the PDBbind data set,^[44] I will use it in the following as being interchangeable with ΔG , which I reflect also in the notation.

⁷ Another possibility would be an incorrect reference structure, which cannot be excluded as it is unpublished, and it is unknown how it was generated.

⁸ Obviously, poses which are scored less good, i.e. Best-2 to Best-9, still have to be considered more unlikely than the pose scored better. This fact is integrated into the multipose binding model by weighting the elements by their Boltzmann probabilities.

In general, a positive correlation between Best-1 scores respectively averaged energies and experimentally determined binding energies could be observed (cf. Figure 6 and Table 5). When comparing *AutoDock Vina* scores and the experimentally determined K_D values (converted to ΔG to allow for easy comparison) with a linear regression, however, the regressions yield coefficients far from the optimum.

Nevertheless, all evaluation methods (Best-1, mean of Best-9 energies, Boltzmann-weighted average of Best-9) succeed to predict the ranks of interaction strength correctly with a maximum of one outlier.

Although quantitative correlation is not achieved in the expected manner, it must be noted, that the standard error of the *AutoDock Vina* score was estimated to be 2.75–2.85 kcal/mol.^[44] The differences in score are significantly less in the examined case, and should be therefore considered to be in the range of uncertainty.

Table 4: DNA sequences used in the computational studies, with corresponding K_D values.

Name	Sequence of top strand (5' → 3')	K_D , PyBAPPA [#] / μM	K_D , PheBAPPA [#] / μM
Dickerson DNA*	CGCG AATT CGCG	n.a.	n.a.
AAATTT	GGC AAATTT CAG [#]	0.229 ± 0.063	0.724 ± 0.089
AATTT	GGCG AATTT CGC [#]	0.334 ± 0.040	1.2 ± 0.1
AATT	GGCG AATT CAGC [#]	1.0 ± 0.2	1.8 ± 0.1
AAGTT	GGCG AAGTT CGC [#]	0.396 ± 0.072	9.1 ± 2.8
AGATT	GGCG AGATT CGC [#]	1.9 ± 0.1	10.2 ± 2.2
AAGCTT	GGC AAGCTT CGC [#]	6.3 ± 0.8	> 15
GGCCC	GGCA GGCC CAGC [#]	n.d. [§]	n.d. [§]

* : This sequence was the first DNA crystallized in B-DNA form (PDB structure: 1BNA), and determined by the working group of Dickerson.^[46] Therefore it is often named “Dickerson” DNA. In this context it is important to note that it contains an AATT element, to which BAPPA binds. “n.a.” = not available.

: All of these sequences were derived from the hairpin structures tested by Sánchez et al.^[19] However, the hairpin loop region is missing, resulting in normal B-DNA molecules. The K_D values were determined for hairpin DNA.

§ : “n.d.” = not determinable, as the K_D value was too high for determination with the method employed by Sánchez et al.^[19]

Table 5: **Results from docking of PyBAPPA and PheBAPPA with AutoDock Vina.** Given is the DNA sequence that was docked to, as well as the score for the best pose (ΔG_{best}) as computed by AutoDock Vina, and the normal (left) and Boltzmann-weighted (right) average scores (ΔG_{avg}) for the Best-9 poses, respectively.

DNA	ΔG_{best} / kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔG_{avg} / kcal mol ⁻¹		ΔG_{best} / kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔG_{avg} / kcal mol ⁻¹	
	PyBAPPA			PheBAPPA		
AAATTT	-9.3	-8.97	-9.03	-9.3	-9.13	-9.15
AATTT	-9.2	-8.91	-8.96	-9.2	-8.94	-9.01
AATT	-9.2	-8.98	-9.01	-9.2	-9.06	-9.07
AAGTT	-9.2	-8.82	-8.88	-9.2	-8.87	-8.91
AGATT	-9.2	-8.80	-8.92	-9.3	-8.89	-9.00
AAGCTT	-9.0	-8.66	-8.74	-9.0	-8.77	-8.80
GGCCC	-8.8	-8.54	-8.58	-9.0	-8.50	-8.62

Figure 6: **Correlation of AutoDock Vina predictions with experimentally determined ΔG values.** PheBAPPA 1 and PyBAPPA 2 were docked with AutoDock Vina to B-DNA models of the sequences given in Table 4. Experimentally determined K_D values were transformed into ΔG values by the thermodynamic relationship $\Delta G = RT \cdot \ln(K_D)$. **A1)** and **B1)** give predicted ΔG of the poses ranked Best-x by the scoring function for different DNA sequences (black circles: AAATTT, green crosshairs: AATT, red triangles up: AATT, cyan diamonds: AGATT, blue crosses: AAGTT, magenta triangles down: AAGCTT, grey cubes: GGCCC) for PyBAPPA and PheBAPPA, respectively. **A2)** and **B2)** give ΔG of the poses ranked best (Best-1, black circles), unweighted average (red triangles), and Boltzmann-weighted average of the 9 poses ranked best (green crosses). Optimal correlation would be achieved on the blue line. Other solid lines are linear regressions for predicted ΔG , coefficients are given in the Appendix. Data points for which K_D values were unavailable are neglected.

Drawback of docking with *AutoDock Vina*

Despite the promising results for dodecamer-DNA docking, the docking approach via *AutoDock Vina* was considered to have a major drawback: when docking to the NCP, it seemed unfunctional to use a box-based design like it is employed by *AutoDock Vina*.

In the NCP, DNA and histone proteins are brought very close together, so a definition of a box allowing unambiguously docking to the DNA only (as the interaction determination of small molecules with the histone protein was out of the scope of this work) was considered impossible.

Furthermore, *AutoDock Vina's* box design makes it complicated to approach the mapping of the nucleosomal DNA minor groove in an exhaustive and systematic way. If it was possible to address each nucleotide as a single box, this might lead to neglected optimal poses in between nucleotide steps, whereas a box containing multiple nucleotides might lead to redundancy in the data: optimal poses could be found multiple times in different boxes, even when it was intended to address the next nucleotide step already.

*3.2.1.3. Employing a different approach: local optimization with *szybki**

Therefore, I decided to address this question with another approach – the automated placement of ligands through the DNA minor groove, followed by energy optimization.

For energy optimization I used *szybki*^[47]. As a preliminary test, I optimized PheBAPPA in the provided reference structure. Upon optimization, however, the ligand's main phenyl moiety left the DNA minor groove largely, resulting in a RMSD of approximately 3.5 Å to the reference structure. Testing different parameters, I was able to identify a set of settings that reproduced the reference structure more closely (cf. Table 6).

It seems that *szybki* overestimated the electrostatic interactions, as a neglect of Coulomb interaction made optimized and reference structure more similar. Employing the more accurate Poisson-Boltzmann solvation model, the RMSD decreased further to a final value of 0.46 Å.

Examining the van-der-Waals interactions, they were found to be considerably stronger for the *noCoulomb* and *PB* settings, but were obviously overcompensated by the electrostatic interactions ($E_{\text{total}} = -1186.34$ kcal/mol for the *recommended* settings). Evaluating the other settings with the Poisson-Boltzmann model, it could be shown that they are indeed non-optimal.

Table 6: **RMSD and szybki calculated energies for different optimization settings.** The energy optimizations with *szybki* were evaluated for successful conservation of the reference pose of the unpublished NMR derived DNA-ligand structure for PheBAPPA 1. The different settings of *szybki* are given with the corresponding RMSD (compared to the hydrogen optimized NMR structure), as well as the calculated energy values. E_{vdw} means energy contributions of van-der-Waals interactions, E_{total} corresponds to total energy calculated without respecting solvent, $E_{total, PB}$ includes the implicit Poisson-Boltzmann solvent model. The results indicate that a Poisson-Boltzmann solvation model is necessary to create results in agreement with experimental derived structures.

*: zero per definitionem.

setting	RMSD / Å	E_{vdw} / kcal mol ⁻¹	E_{total} / kcal mol ⁻¹	$E_{total, PB}$ / kcal mol ⁻¹
NMR structure	-0.08	-14.34	135.00	146.63
Honly	0*	-13.36	31.08	43.97
recommended	3.49	-10.02	-1186.34	27.75
noCoulomb	0.87	-19.40	81.13	-
PB	0.46	-19.11	-	19.08

3.2.1.4. Redocking of PheBAPPA to Dickerson DNA with *groover-szybki*

After energy optimization was successfully implemented, I had to find a way to conduct a systematic and exhaustive search through the whole minor groove. Therefore, I decided to reduce the dimensionality of the search space. Whereas conventional rigid ligand docking employs a six-dimensional search space (three dimensions of grid points, three dimensions of possible rotations), *AutoDock Vina* is employing an even higher dimensional search space with its use of rotamer search (e.g. 10 rotatable bonds in PheBAPPA). I, however, wanted to produce only one (optimal) pose for a series of points, following the groove's nature. For details on the computational approach behind this *groover-szybki* based approach, the reader is referred to the Experimental Part, Chapter 5.12.

To evaluate the reliability of this *groover-szybki* approach compared to *AutoDock Vina*, I tested the redocking of PheBAPPA to the unpublished NMR structure provided by Mateo I. Sánchez again.

This allows us to compare the *AutoDock Vina* based docking directly with the newly developed *groover-szybki* approach.

Therefore, PheBAPPA was extracted from its NMR structure, and was placed at grid points following the shape of the DNA minor groove with *groover* (for details, cf. Chapter 5.12.1 in the Experimental Part). To increase the sampling density, i.e. smoothness of the grid, the ligand was placed in ten equivalent distances per base-pair step, resulting in steps of approximately 0.5 Å each. The conformation of the ligand was held fixed, but its orientation in the minor groove was adjusted by a reconstruction of the orientation from the original reference structure.

The thereby generated “start” structures were energetically optimized by *szybki* with the adapted settings. This led to one (optimal) pose per grid point. Energy values of the optimized structures were extracted and plotted against their position. This position number corresponded roughly to the base-pair position on which the center of the ligand could be found.

Results from PheBAPPA redocking

The results (cf. Figure 7a) indicate that the *groover-szybki* approach is able to find sufficient poses of PheBAPPA (i.e. poses with a RMSD of < 2.5 Å from the reference structure) within the first 9 best-ranked poses, exactly as *AutoDock Vina*. Furthermore, the applied RMSD criterion is even stricter here, as it is calculated as an all-atom RMSD including hydrogens, whereas for evaluation of *AutoDock Vina* a heavy-atom RMSD was used.

In contrast to *AutoDock Vina*, however, the *groover-szybki*-based approach enables us to evaluate the minor groove in an exhaustive and systematic way, thereby generating “in silico footprints”⁹ of the DNA-ligand interaction on the ligand’s way through the DNA minor groove (cf. Figure 7b).

3.2.1.5. Docking of PyBAPPA to known interaction sequences with groover

To evaluate the performance of the *groover-szybki* approach in predicting correctly the interaction strength to sequences with known K_D values (analogously to the correlation of *AutoDock Vina* derived energy values to K_D values), I conducted the following experiment:

⁹ This term is used in analogy to the “in silico footprinting” described by Anthony et al.^[24] There, however, it is generated by MD simulation and not resolved to specific nucleotide positions but only to time frames from which the interaction sequence is then derived manually. Note also the analogy of “in silico footprints” to the DNase I or hydroxyl radical generated “footprints” described later in this work.

All known subsequences were modelled with *Web 3DNA* in one continuous strand (to reduce the number of substrates to be evaluated), and PyBAPPA molecules were docked with the *groover-szybki* approach to the whole DNA minor groove. This allowed to generate an "in silico footprint" of DNA-ligand interaction. I expected to be able to derive an indicator of interaction from this data which could be correlated to the experimentally determined K_D values.

However, the results (cf. Figure 8) were unexpected. The *groover-szybki* model found multiple sites with extremely strong interactions, although the majority of points fluctuated only slightly around its median level.

The energy values have a mean of 10.2 kcal/mol, median = 13.3 kcal/mol, whereas the first quartile (i.e. the $\frac{1}{4}$ of all points with the lowest energies) shows values from 9.5 kcal/mol to -344.2 kcal/mol (which were cut from the figure to increase visibility of the other points). As no correlation of these strong interactions with the order of K_D values could be found, and they fulfilled a statistically robust outlier test^[48] ($E < Q1 - 1.5 \text{ IQR}$, i.e. $E < -2.39$ kcal/mol, or $E > Q3 + 1.5 \text{ IQR}$, i.e. $E > 29.3$ kcal/mol; IQR: interquartile range = $Q3 - Q1$, i.e. $\text{IQR} = 7.91$ kcal/mol; Q1/3: first and third quartile, respectively), they were considered outliers.¹⁰

Considering furthermore the general outline of the energy function over base pairs, it seems indeed possible to visually identify "footprints" of slightly decreased energy values in the neighborhood of the known interaction sequences. However, due to the small signal-to-noise ratio it seems impossible to discriminate those footprints against non-interacting positions with statistical means.

¹⁰ Note that normal outlier tests may be hampered by non-normal distributed data. If in silico footprinting would generate the expected results, this would be the case. Therefore, a statistically robust outlier test, relying on quartiles, was employed.

Figure 7: **Redocking of PheBAPPA to Dickerson DNA with groover-szybki.** **A)** Total energy of poses generated with the groover-szybki approach for redocking of PheBAPPA **1** to Dickerson DNA. The poses were ranked according to their binding energy as computed by szybki, and are drawn as their rank number. The RMSD value of each pose to the reference structure can be found on the x-axis. The RMSD threshold of 2.5 Å compared to the reference structure is displayed as a red line. Poses that can be found in the lower left corner indicate successful redocking. **B)** “In silico footprint” of the DNA-ligand interaction for docking of PheBAPPA **1** throughout the DNA minor groove of Dickerson DNA. PheBAPPA was placed at each position with groover, optimized with szybki, and the total energy of the optimized complex extracted. The black line at nt position 19 indicates the position of the ligand in the reference structure, the red lines give the limits of poses with RMSD values of less than 2.5 Å compared to the reference structure.

Figure 8: ***In silico footprint for known sequences with strong interaction.*** Energy values of PyBAPPA 2 interacting with DNA consisting of all known interacting sequences in a continuous manner (from Sánchez et al.^[19]) were determined by docking as previously described. Strong interactions or repulsions lying far outside from the average energy can be seen irregularly (note that the strong interactions pointing downwards reach values of up to -344.2 kcal/mol, but are not shown for clarity of visualization). The total energy median (red line) serves as a guide to the eye. The nucleotide indicated in the text band has the nearest phosphate to the central pyridine nitrogen of PyBAPPA. Slightly lowered energy values can be seen in the vicinity of expected strong binding sequences ((A/T)_n-tracts), but cannot be identified by statistical means because of their low signal-to-noise ratio.

3.2.1.6. *Energy fluctuations are large even for near positions in space*

I shortly want to highlight the unexpectedly large energy fluctuations for positions near in space when employing the *groover-szybki* approach.

Expecting a smooth indication of "sweet spots" corresponding to the ligand's footprint, it was very surprising to see such a big variability (i.e. noise) in energy values. The transformation of ligand conformations between close-by grid points was evaluated by visual inspection, and was found, unaffected by highly variable energy values, rather smooth. It was suspected that this high variability of energy values might result from trapped optimization process, i.e. finding local minima of the scoring function instead of global minima. As we were interested in positions being able to reproduce the expected binding mode, it was decided to accept the highly variable energy values and to continue with this calculation approach.

3.2.2. *Going beyond the limits of docking*

After successful docking of the binding moiety, PyBAPPA or PheBAPPA, the next step was to generate an energetically optimal pose for a multivalent ligand. However, it is computationally unfeasible to generate all possible conformations of a ligand with a large number of heavy atoms.¹¹ Considering our aim, the simplest multivalent ligand we can envision is consisting of two binding moieties and one linker. As PyBAPPA is consisting of 28 heavy atoms already, we must assume that the smallest multivalent ligand possible consists of at least $2 \times 28 = 56$ heavy atoms.

As an increase in the number of heavy atoms with rotatable bonds makes the rotamer generation computationally more expensive in an exponential way, another approach had to be applied.

3.2.2.1. *Deployment of a fragment-based approach*

To stretch the limits of docking, I chose to reduce the (unfeasibly) large conformational space of a multivalent ligand by employing a fragment-based approach. For this, its chemical entities were docked separately, and then connected in an energetically and chemical sensible way.

A model ligand **3** was prepared previously in our working group by B. Heinrich.^[49] It was chosen to evaluate the building blocks of this model ligand by fragmentation into PyBAPPA binder moieties containing a part of the linker (to map the influence of the linker, too; this fragment is further called

¹¹ For example, the time needed to find docking poses with *AutoDock Vina* increases exponentially with the number of heavy atoms.^[44]

“capped PyBAPPA”, and possesses a terminal carbon labelled C_{Ω}), and a separate linker fragment (“linker”). Capped PyBAPPA **4** and its relation to the whole model ligand **3** is indicated in Scheme 2.

Scheme 2: Structure formula of model ligand (3) and capped PyBAPPA (4). Capped PyBAPPA is consisting of PyBAPPA plus the beginning of the linking scaffold, and is terminated by a methyl group at C_{Ω} (marked red). The connection point to the model ligand is indicated by a wavy line. Resonance structures of the amidinium groups are omitted for clarity.

3.2.2.2. Simplifying docking by knowledge-based restrictions

As we supposed to know the most likely binding mode for BAPPA derivatives already from its unpublished NMR structure, we decided to reproduce the binding mode of the PyBAPPA moiety at every grid point by reconstructing the ligand into the minor groove with help of the program *groover*. Subsequent energy optimization was supposed to help to find the energetically minimal pose at a given spatial location, starting from the reproduced binding mode.

3.2.3. Capped PyBAPPA docked to DNA with the *groover-szybki* approach: description of generated docking data set

Drawing together the previous efforts, two main experiments were performed: Assessment of ligand-DNA interaction in (i) linear DNA, and (ii) in nucleosomal DNA.

3.2.3.1. Docking capped PyBAPPA to nucleosomal DNA (Widom 601 sequence)

Docking of capped PyBAPPA **4** to nucleosomal DNA of the Widom 601 sequence was done by choosing PDB structure 3LZ1 (containing the crystal structure of nucleosome core particle NCP-601) as starting point, and constructing a fine one-dimensional grid through the whole DNA minor groove. PyBAPPA was placed in its suspected binding conformation to every grid point with the help of *groover*, and so-generated structures were optimized in terms of energy with *szybki*.

The results indicate strong interactions every 10 bp, at positions which roughly correspond to outward-facing minor grooves (SHL -6.0, -5.0, ... , +6.0). At nucleotides of the inward-facing minor grooves, a strong repulsion force is visible.

Figure 9: ***In silico footprint for nucleosomal DNA.*** Energy values for the interaction of NCP-601 with capped PyBAPPA **4** were derived from simplified docking, i.e. placement through the DNA minor groove with *groover* and energy optimization with *szybki*. Higher energy values indicate a less likely binding, whereas lower energy values indicate preferred binding sites. The red line at 0 kcal/mol serves as a guide to the eye. The nucleotide which phosphate is nearest to the central pyridine nitrogen is indicated below in a text band. In general, inward-facing DNA minor grooves show high energy values, making interaction of capped PyBAPPA with the nucleosomal DNA very unlikely. The energy differences between outward-facing DNA minor grooves are rather small.

When evaluating the 3-dimensional structure, it became clear that it was not easy to map the positions of the ligand unambiguously to specific nucleotides (cf. also the discussion of this topic in the Appendix). I chose therefore to map the ligand position to the nucleotide which belonged to the phosphate nearest to the central pyridine nitrogen atom of the ligand (and which belonged to the chosen reference strand of DNA). It is therefore important to note, that conclusions about steric (in-)accessibility of positions are difficult when made from the nucleotide sequence only.

The observed repulsions were identified as mainly due to collision of capped PyBAPPA with arginine side chains of the histone octamer. *Groover* places the BAPPA derivative moiety without respect to pre-existent structures into the DNA minor groove – the result is a steric clash which is energetically costly. Energy optimization with *szybki* leads to an evasive motion of the BAPPA derivative moiety then, but often some atoms are trapped (e.g. interlocked aromatic rings) and local minima (of high total energy in comparison to other minima) are found at which energy optimization stops.

3.2.3.2. Interactions of capped PyBAPPA with linear DNA (Widom 601 sequence)

For linear DNA of the same sequence (generated with *W3DNA*), the *groover-szybki* model found multiple outliers (as determined by the statistical robust outlier test described before) with extremely strong interactions ($E_{\text{total}} = -50 - -2989$ kcal/mol), which deviated very strongly from the distribution of total energy values (cf. Figure 10; mean = -45.7 kcal/mol; median = -28.4 kcal/mol). These outliers occurred with a strong periodicity of 5 bp, increasing the evidence for artifacts. As they passed the outlier test outlined above, they were not considered any further.

Apart from that, it seemed even harder to identify statistically robust "footprints" in the energy values. A few positions seemed to present visual evidence of favorable interactions, but they could not be further specified in an unbiased manner. Therefore, it was not possible to correlate the results of this model to the experimentally derived data. It can therefore be used as a qualitative model only, as quantitation would require a scoring function able to treat in silico footprints.¹²

¹² This is the same problem the approach by Anthony et al.^[24] suffers from.

3.2.3.3. Comparison of linear and nucleosomal DNA form

The energy optimization of *szbki* considers not only the intramolecular energy of the ligand, but also its interactions with the receptor. It is therefore not possible to compare the results of capped PyBAPPA docking to linear and nucleosomal DNA in a quantitative manner. Nevertheless, it is possible to visualize qualitatively the strong influence of the histone proteins on ligand binding, in contrast to the interactions of the ligand with DNA in its linear form.

The scoring function of *szybki* returns a value termed “total energy”, which the developers most likely designed to reflect total energy of binding, ΔG_{bind} . If this scoring function would be indeed able to reproduce the experimental binding energy, this would indicate little binding of the capped PyBAPPA fragment to the NCP. Nearly all observed energy values are above 0 kcal/mol (thus indicating no binding) for nucleosomal DNA, whereas they are constantly below 0 kcal/mol (thus indicating binding) for linear DNA.

Figure 10: *In silico footprint for the linear Widom 601 DNA.* Energy values of capped PyBAPPA interacting with modelled linear DNA of the Widom 601 sequence were determined by docking as previously described. Statistically tested outliers were removed for clarity of visualization. The median of total energy (red line) serves as a guide to the eye. Favorable interactions can be seen e.g. around nt positions -43, -15, or +25 as slight depressions of the total energy. Position of the interaction is mapped by determining the nucleotide of the phosphate nearest to capped PyBAPPA’s pyridine nitrogen.

3.2.4. Constructing an optimal multivalent ligand

Having the data on interaction of binder fragments with the target NCP-601 in hand, I wanted to find the optimal combination of binding moieties according to the aim set for this work: to create a multivalent ligand stretching one of the nucleosomal supergrooves.

3.2.4.1. Determination of optimal binder combinations

As none of the tested super-helix locations were clearly favored over others, I chose to handle the problem exhaustively and connected all optimized poses on the minor groove grid with each other, resulting in a dataset of 3 796 390 entries. This tests all possible combinations, also very unlikely ones, but seemed to be the most reliable way to handle the uncertainty from the quantitatively not confirmable data.

Of the complete set on entries (cf. Figure 11) only a very small part was considered to be of interest – the energetically most optimal entries, which were the closest to each other (as this would make connecting them more feasible¹³). Focus was set on a range of distances from 0 to 20 Å to bridge between the connection points, considering the 10 entries best-in-class (i.e. lowest energy for a given distance bin).

Not surprisingly, these entries corresponded to binding moieties spanning a nucleosomal supergroove (abbreviated as SHG: super-helix groove; similarly to the super-helix locations (SHL), I numbered them as SHG 1 to SHG 7 – cf. Table 7 to learn more about the numbering scheme for SHGs). It is known that a single BAPPA derivative molecule stretches the minor groove by a length of approximately 5 nucleotides,^[19] which corresponds well to the approximate length of accessible nucleotides in the outward-facing minor grooves.^[2]

To determine the position of the energetically most interesting BAPPA poses (i.e., the area outlined in red in Figure 11) in terms of SHG position, the SHL of each entry was determined by the program *ruler*. SHLs that bridged a specific super-helical groove were subsequently clustered, whereas positions next to each other were assigned SHG = 0. It came to the eye immediately, that one specific position was favored the most, i.e. containing the most optimal binder combinations: SHG 6, thus connecting the area of nt positions around +60 to -20. Distances bridged by this cluster ranged from 5 Å upwards (cf. Figure 12 and Figure 13).

¹³ It seems unlikely that a linker scaffold not connecting nucleosomal supergrooves, but stretching for example over the histone face, would be energetically more favorable.

This correlates well to the 11–18 Å distance Dervan and co-workers had to bridge when they constructed the linker for their hairpin polyamide dimer “clamp” bridging the super-helical groove.^[2]

Unlike Dervan and co-workers, who chose to address SHG 4, i.e. connecting nucleotides -40 and +40, the nucleotides directly opposite of the nucleosome dyad, thus creating a centrally positioned clamp, our results indicate that PyBAPPA binder moieties would be more effective at SHG 6.¹⁴

¹⁴ Note that the work from Dervan and co-workers is only partially comparable to our work and aim. They addressed specific sequences of a nucleosome core particle containing the human α -satellite DNA, i.e. NCP146, by constructing highly sequence-specific hairpin polyamides to stabilize the NCP, whereas we aim for a more general application.

Figure 11: **Construction of all binder moiety combinations.** Energy values were determined for any combination between two binder moieties (i.e., capped PyBAPPA) that were docked to NCP-601 like previously described. The distance between C_{Ω} atoms of two moieties was measured, and plotted against the linear combination of total energy values of the two moieties compared. The most interesting part is the lower left corner (marked red), i.e. small distances between C_{Ω} atoms with a low sum of energy values, making an energetically favorable multivalent ligand, i.e. a linked version of the both corresponding binding moieties, more likely.

Figure 12: **Clustering of most promising binder combinations.** For each distance bin (bandwidth= 1 Å, i.e. bin 1: 0–1 Å, bin 2: 1–2 Å, ..., upper limit 20 Å) the 10 binder combinations with lowest energies were identified, and plotted in regard to the nucleotide positions they connected. These clusters can be assigned to the super-helical grooves (SHG), as indicated. SHG 6 contains the most promising binder combinations for multivalent binding (cf. Figure 13), whereas SHG 1–5 contain only entries of high energy or very short distances (not shown). Black triangles indicate SHG “0”, i.e. binder combinations of moieties lying next to each other, thus not stretching a nucleosomal supergroove. The ligand positions were mapped to the corresponding nucleotides by determining the nearest phosphate.

Figure 13: **Distance to bridge for most promising binder combinations.** Magenta circles indicate binder combinations connecting SHG 6, whereas black triangles are binder combinations connecting neighboring binder moieties (SHG “0”). The distance to bridge between specific binder combinations is presented against the sum of total energies for the two binding moieties. Small energies are favorable for binding. As can be seen, the distance to bridge varies strongly even for similar sums of total energies. This indicates a binding scenario with flexibility in the nucleotides to be targeted.

Table 7: **List of bridged super-helix locations (SHL) for a specific super-helical groove (SHG).** Note that nucleotides at SHLs ± 7.0 are experiencing already very strong end effects, and were therefore generally not computed. SHG = 0 represents binder moieties that lie next to each other without stretching a super-helical groove.

SHG	SHL / ~ nt pos	SHL / ~ nt pos
0	-	-
1	“-7.0” / -70	+1.0 / +10
2	-6.0 / -60	+2.0 / +20
3	-5.0 / -50	+3.0 / +30
4	-4.0 / -40	+4.0 / +40
5	-3.0 / -30	+5.0 / +50
6	-2.0 / -20	+6.0 / +60
7	-1.0 / -10	“+7.0” / +70

3.2.4.2. Determination of optimal linker length

To construct a linker of optimal shape, I focused first on the chemical structure of the linker and the influence the chemical structure has on its three-dimensional conformations. Subsequently, I deduced a possible chemical structure to construct a linker that fits to the optimal binder combinations previously determined. The linker structure to be examined is inspired by the linker moiety of model ligand **3**, and is given in Scheme 3.

Lessons to be learned from the evaluation of $n(C)$ vs. distance

To determine the distance bridged by a linker in its native, relaxed state, random conformations of the linker *in vacuo* were generated with *omega* and energetically optimized with *szybki* employing the implicit Poisson-Boltzmann solvent. This data set was then statistically evaluated for the distance between the two terminal C_ω , corresponding to the distance bridged by the linker if it was connected with two binding moieties.

The linker length, i.e. the number of methylene bridges in the hydrocarbon chain (cf. Scheme 3), in model ligand **3** was $n = 5$, but *in silico* I explored also $n = 3$ and $n = 7$. *Omega* generated random conformations *in vacuo* of which the top-1000 in regard to low energy were selected. Subsequently, an energy optimization with *szybki* with the PB solvation model followed. All of this was intended to model the most likely behavior of the linker moiety in a water environment, assuming that the linker does not bury in hydrophobic areas of the NCP, but it is in steady contact with water, from solvation of the multivalent ligand to binding.

Scheme 3: **Structure formula of the linker moiety with $n=3$, $n=5$, $n=7$.** In model ligand **3**, $n=5$. When considering the linker, C_ω terminates as a methyl group, but when the linker is connected to a binder moiety, it is replaced by C_Ω as a methylene group.

Figure 14: **Energy distribution for linkers with $n=3$, $n=5$, $n=7$.** The distance between C_{ω} atoms of 1000 optimized linker moiety structures with different lengths of hydrocarbon chains was evaluated for their relative occurrence probability. The results indicate an almost equal probability for bridging distances of 6.3 or 14.9 Å, respectively, for $n=3$. For $n=5$, the most likely distances to be bridged are 7.1 Å or 4.8 Å, whereas for $n=7$ the linker moiety prefers to bridge a distance of 5.5 Å exclusively. Counterintuitively, short linkers span distances of approximately 6 or 15 Å routinely, whereas the longest linker has a clear preference for distances of only 5.5 Å. The density profiles generated can be understood as a guide towards energy distribution, i.e. likelihood, of different linker conformations, and can therefore be used to assess the optimal linker length for different distances to bridge.

n=3

n=5

n=7

Figure 15: **Structures of exemplary linkers with $n=3$, $n=5$, $n=7$.** Exemplary structures for linkers with different n (number of methylene bridges in the hydrocarbon chain) help to explain the unexpected trend of shorter distances between the two C_ω with longer hydrocarbon chains. A strong π -stacking can be seen for the short $n=3$ linker, which is supplemented with a strong hydrophobic interaction of the long hydrocarbon chains with $n=7$. The “long” conformation of $n=3$ is not π -stacking, and the difference between “short” and “long” conformation of $n=5$ seems to be due to flexibility of the hydrocarbon chain.

Counterintuitively, a longer linker length led to reduction of the bridged distance (cf. Figure 14). Considering the form of the corresponding energy density profiles, the n=3 linker seems to be a switchable linker between a 6 and 15 Å state, whereas the n=5 linker bridges distances of 5 or 7 Å optimally, and the n=7 linker bridges very selectively only 5.5 Å.

Upon inspection of the generated three-dimensional structures (cf. Figure 15), it became clear that chemical intuitivity (longer hydrocarbon chain → longer distance bridged) neglected two effects influencing the distance bridged significantly: i) π -stacking of the triazole rings, and ii) hydrophobic interactions between the hydrocarbon chains.

Connecting binder and linker in silico

To link the optimal binder and linker combination *in silico*, a set of both had to be chosen.

Therefore, the energetically most optimal binder combinations were evaluated for their suitability to be bridged by one of the linkers. As the best binder combinations showed continuously large distances to bridge (in the range of 13–18 Å), the n=3 linker was chosen. The terminal C ω methyl groups of the linker moiety were aligned to the terminal C Ω methyl groups of the binder moieties, and the C Ω groups removed. One of the hydrogens of the C ω groups was removed, and the open valence was used to connect the linker with the binder moieties.

A further round of energy minimization with *szymbki* led to the structure presented in Figure 16 as a plausible multivalent ligand conformation.¹⁵

¹⁵ As there are also binder combinations with rather short distances (5–9 Å) in the list of energetically optimal binder combinations, I do not want to exclude that model ligand **3** will be functional, too. The computational results can lead our research in the right direction, but experimental proof is compulsory.

Figure 16: **Proposed three-dimensional structure of a multivalent nucleosome sensor.** **A)** The proposed ligand (dark green spheres) is bound to nucleosomal DNA (white and blue surface representation); in the background the histone octamer (light colored spheres) can be seen. The stretched nucleosomal supergroove is SHG 6, the upper left corner shows the DNA exit site. **B)** A three-dimensional stick representation of the proposed ligand. Two PyBAPPA binding moieties can bind to nucleosomal DNA. They are bridged by a $n=3$ linker. Hydrogens are omitted for clarity.

3.2.5. Summary

In the preceding chapter, I have shown that the Widom 601 sequence contains nucleotide stretches which qualify to be binding positions for BAPPA derivatives. Drawing from the literature it was not possible to decide if those positions are blocked completely in the NCP or if they were available for interactions.

AutoDock Vina was found to perform reasonably well for DNA-ligand docking, but it was abandoned for systematic reasons.

I developed an innovative method for ligand placement into DNA minor grooves, which will also be suitable for placement into DNA major grooves. This method allows automation of an often manually performed step, and enabled me to evaluate a large number of ligand positions throughout the nucleosomal DNA minor groove.

In silico footprinting with *groover-szybki* was in principle successful, but the resulting signal-to-noise ratio was too low to correlate experimentally determined affinities with the computational model, because a scoring function for in silico footprinting is missing and out of the scope of this work.

The computational evaluation of the linker moiety led to valuable insights about the relationship between the number of methylene bridges in the hydrocarbon chain and the bridged distance.

Finally, my fragment-based approach with knowledge-based restrictions of the search space allowed to generate a plausible pose for a multivalent nucleosome sensor. Under the current limitations of the system, SHG 6 was identified as the most promising nucleosomal supergroove for multivalent ligand binding based on BAPPA derivatives.

3.3. Implementation of footprinting for detection of interactions with high base-pair resolution

In this chapter I describe how I established and developed the method of capillary electrophoresis (CE) with laser-induced fluorescence detection (LIF) in our working group to measure interactions of small molecules with DNA which was end-labelled with a fluorophore.

The basics of this technique are described in the Introduction (Chapter 1.4.2). The reader is further referred to excellent protocols for DNase I footprinting,^[50] hydroxyl radical footprinting,^[51] footprinting of nucleosomal DNA,^[52] and an overview article describing the method more generally.^[53]

3.3.1. Setting up the footprinting process

In total, 80 samples were run on an ABI PRISM 310 Genetic Analyzer.

The DNA needed to detect footprints of the ligands was selectively end-labelled on the 5'-end of the upper strand (cf. Scheme 4). The 6FAM (6-carboxyfluorescein) dye was used for PCR end-labelling, while the only available size standard was labelled with BTO.¹⁶

Each sample returned a time-series of fluorescence emissions (“trace”). The amount of fluorescence emission is assumed to be in linear correlation with the amount of DNA passing the detector, while the specific time point correlates with the size (correctly: the electrophoretic mobility) of the detected DNA fragment.

3.3.1.1. Data evaluation

A major point of concern is the evaluation of the generated data.

Our data set consists of descriptions of the peaks with multiple variables: i) the called size (i.e. the size that was assigned to a specific peak by comparison to the size standard peaks), ii) the peak height and peak area (these correlate strongly linear for small peaks but start to deviate more for stronger signals), iii) descriptive metadata, i.e. from which sample this peak was generated, the concentration of the sample, etc.

¹⁶ BTO is a proprietary dye which composition is not disclosed.^[54a] Therefore, only speculations are possible on the chemical nature of this dye. However, concluding from the company's patent filing^[54b] it can be speculated that BTO is DY-632 or DY-520XL. These dyes are indeed chemically significantly different from fluorescein (PubChem CID: 56927795^[54c]).

The final aim of the data evaluation is to generate a concentration-dependent series of relative peak heights. For this, the ratio of peak area to total DNA area must be known to identify peaks that have changed in their peak area ratio due to cleavage blocking by ligand interaction.

Because the saturation of the detector by the full-length DNA is making it impossible to determine the integrated peak density of the whole sample in one recording, I had to employ a different approach than the one suggested in the literature (Hampshire^[53] suggests to use a band-based approach, i.e. to calculate the fraction of the density of the band of interest to the whole lane density). As 90% of the DNA has to stay uncut to ensure so-called single-hit kinetics (i.e. a maximum of one cut per DNA molecule to generate reliable footprinting data), within the given dynamic range of the CE-LIF instrument to hand it is impossible to realize a non-saturating recording of cleavage peaks as well as of uncut DNA.

The aim of determining ratios between peaks from different traces is to be able to account for differences in the DNA amount subjected to analysis (which easily occurs by pipetting errors, non-specific binding to reaction tube walls, etc.). Acknowledging that a precise solution would not be possible, I made the following assumption: even when not knowing the exact DNA amount subjected to analysis, we would still be able to find a signal which would stay unchanged if there was no DNA-ligand interaction in the surrounding of the corresponding nucleotide.

I therefore chose to select a reference peak in a region of expected non-binding, i.e. at a base pattern for which interaction seemed unlikely by our current knowledge (binding is expected for R₄ tracts, i.e. a combination of at least four A or T nucleotides in a row).¹⁷ Wanting to exclude the unfavorable end-effects (i.e. not choosing peaks within the first and last 20 nucleotides minimum) and choosing the largest G/C-rich patch possible, this led to determination of the region of nt 63–86 as a region for which binding would most likely not be the case. When considering general peak distribution, a peak which would not deviate substantially in samples with different ligand concentrations was favorable. Further, a higher peak would be favorable for alignment of multiple traces due to the increased signal-to-noise ratio which makes alignment more precise – this led to selection of the peak at nt 63.5 as our reference peak.

3.3.1.2. *Problems with size calling, peak regularity, sequencing*

When analyzing the pattern of cleavage, I noticed a strong irregularity in the decimal places of the called peak sizes (e.g. peaks occurred at ..., 59.8, 61.3, 63.5, 65.3, 67.6, ...). I expected the

¹⁷ This is a usual procedure in footprinting, and employed by other authors as well, even by the most unbiased method available to date.^[57,58]

difference to the previous peak to be a multiple of 1.0 (even when considering that not every base undergoes cleavage, the peak size should increase in a systematic way), but this was not the case (cf. Figure 18).

I suspect that the size standard is not working correctly for the DNA we use. It was shown by Hahn et al.^[55] that a difference in the chemical nature of the dye might influence its electrophoretic mobility, and therefore would compromise the size calling. Comparing rhodamine to fluorescein dyes, differences in called size as big as 11 bp are possible for the same DNA fragment, whereas the difference inside one dye group still might be as big as 2.5 bp. Furthermore, this difference is size-dependent, and might increase at lower sizes.

I suspect that BTO is differing chemically strongly from the used fluorescein label. This explanation fits to the observation that the full-length fragment was expected to be 147 bp long, but size calling with BTO550 showed a size of ~ 145 bp. The other fragment of known size, the primer, could not be called reliably, because it was too small and could only be called by extrapolation from the smallest size standard fragment at 60 bp. An impurity, which was arbitrarily set to 16.0 bp, helped to align peaks below 60 bp.

Figure 17: **Capillary electrophoresis peaks for the primer and the full-length DNA product, respectively.** Note that the full-length product is expected to generate a peak at 147 nt (but produces 145.4 nt, **B**), and the primer at 18 nt (but produces 8.7 nt (**A**) based on linear extrapolation of the smallest sizing standard peak at 60 nt). Peaks of the size standard are presented in orange, the 6FAM-labelled DNA in blue.

Figure 18: *Size differences to previous peaks for a collection of exemplary footprint trace. Note how the differences are only seldom multiples of 1.0 (marked by horizontal lines), but vary randomly in their decimal place. If the differences were multiples of 1.0, the points were aligned to the horizontal lines, if peak size calling was corrupted in a systematic way, another pattern should be visible.*

For the future, non-proprietary size standards would be the method of choice, e.g. by constructing a size standard with a known dye (LIZ or Atto 633 are commonly used), or injecting more fragments of precisely known DNA sequence and length to develop a safe and sound method to determine the correct DNA fragment length.

Similarly, problems were experienced when performing base sequencing with the Maxam-Gilbert reaction to identify the observed DNA fragments by their sequence. Traditionally, the footprinting fragments are aligned to a DNA ladder which was generated by the G+A selective Maxam-Gilbert reaction. Thereby, guanine and adenine bases are cleaved off, and the strand is cut at those depurinated positions.

The called sizes of this G+A track did not always fit to the expected peaks, especially when comparing DNase I cleavage peaks with the sequencing track.

This is because of the different mechanisms involved in cleaving the bases, and was referred to in the literature in a very concise and clear way.^[56] Figure 20 gives an overview of the different cleavage products and explains how sequencing tracks have to be aligned to the footprinting samples.

Using ddNTPs to produce PCR fragments which are aborted specifically at positions of one nucleotide type (the so-called Sanger dye-primer sequencing procedure, cf. Figure 19 for an illustration of the working principle), in the future it will be possible for our working group to align DNase I footprint substrates to their known sequences with single-base resolution.

Figure 19: *Illustration of the working principle for dye-primer sequencing. From: reference [68].*

Figure 20: **Chemical structures of different cleavage products and the apparent size difference between different sequencing chemistries.** **A)** Indicated are the chemical structures of products generated by the corresponding chemistry. **B)** The observed size difference between same nucleotides when mapped with different sequencing chemistries (Sanger ddNTP termination vs. Maxam-Gilbert cleavage reactions) is varying with the length of the DNA fragment. Figure from He et al.^[56]

3.3.1.3. Optimization of hydroxyl radical and DNase I footprinting conditions

When starting to footprint a new substrate, the reaction conditions for substrate cleavage have to be optimized in such a way that they result in a so-called single hit kinetic. Optimization can be performed in two dimensions: concentration of the reagents and duration of the reaction.

This was done in a systematic approach guided by methodological papers from Connaghan-Jones et al.^[50] and Jain & Tullius^[50].

Hydroxyl radical cleavage was optimized by varying reaction times (1, 2, 3, 4, 8 min), evaluating the evenness of the resulting product peak heights. However, due to a misled interpretation of the literature while preparing the stop solution (stopping by glycerol was performed first; but the glycerol content was too low to stop the reaction effectively) differences could not be detected. When switching to DMSO as stop reagent, the standard cleavage time of 1 min proved to be sufficient for steady peak heights. Further test reactions would need to be performed if it was chosen to continue hydroxyl radical footprinting.

DNase I cleavage was optimized by keeping the cleavage time of 2 min constant, but varying the concentration of DNase I (1.5 mU, 15 mU, 150 mU of DNase I per 100 ng DNA in 50 μ L reaction volume). Indeed, the evenness of the peak heights varied strongly with different DNase I concentrations, but data points were not chosen dense enough to make a final conclusion. The finally chosen dilution (1.5 mU) proved to work sufficiently for the following experiments, but also here, further experiments would justify the chosen dilution in a more systematic way.

3.3.2. *Assessment of DNA-histone interactions by footprinting*

To characterize the DNA-histone interaction (which serves as negative control when footprinting ligand interaction with nucleosomal DNA), two approaches were taken: hydroxyl radical and DNase I cleavage of NCP-601.

3.3.2.1. *Hydroxyl radical footprinting is able to show the histone-DNA interaction pattern (10 bp periodicity)*

When footprinting DNA-histone complexes (NCPs) with hydroxyl radical cleavage, a strong periodic pattern was found (cf. Figure 21a). This pattern, with a periodicity of approximately 10 bp, was reported earlier in the literature for digestion with DNase I, and is determined by the structure of the nucleosome.^[59]

This pattern is characterized by stronger cleavage (more amplitude of signal) at the DNA backbone lying on the outside of the NCP, as opposed by reduced cleavage at the inward-facing DNA. The histone-DNA interaction is effectively protecting the DNA backbone from being cleaved by hydroxyl radicals. However, the hydroxyl radical cleavage is rather unspecific and gives rise to multiple cleavage products. These products overlap in their electrophoretic mobility and thus result in a signal of overlapping peaks. Determination of peak areas is therefore impossible, or would require computationally intensive fitting of one Lorentzian curves for each peak (cf. for this approach e.g. Das et al.^[60]). However, background determination is only possible before and after the measurement, so that fitting of multiple Lorentzian curves is still an approximation only.

As an alternative, raw peak heights might be used for further characterization of interactions with the nucleosomal DNA. As *PeakScanner* was unable to export raw peak heights without recognizing the peaks correctly, this was not pursued further.¹⁸

3.3.2.2. *DNase I footprinting shows prominent periodic peaks, but little cleavage at other nucleotides*

The generated DNase I footprints showed very prominent peaks with a periodicity of ~10 bp. However, only small signals were obtained for the other nucleotide peaks (cf. Figure 21b).

¹⁸ Nevertheless, footprinting by hydroxyl radical cleavage might be attractive for mapping interactions of small molecules with nucleosomal DNA due to its superiority (in regard to positional resolution and peak height evenness) to DNase I footprinting. Our working group is currently developing an approach to export and align peak heights of hydroxyl radical cleavage products from the proprietary fsa file format.

DNase I footprinting of PyBAPPA interacting with histone-DNA complexes is therefore predicted to be unable to characterize interactions in an exhaustive way. This is because, in contrast to small hydroxyl radicals, DNase I is a rather big enzyme, having difficulties to reach into the DNA minor grooves that lie buried in the NCP (cf. for an illustration of this Figure 3 from an early paper on DNA accessibility in the NCP by Klug and Lutter^[61]). Only the few positions at the outward-facing minor grooves are accessible, and are therefore cleaved preferentially. A correspondence between the cleavage sites preferred by hydroxyl radicals and those preferred by DNase I can be seen.

The Widom 601 sequence, as one of the strongest positioning sequence known so far, is complicating the cleavage of the DNA backbone further by binding extremely strong to the histone core. The interaction that has to be disturbed by DNase I before being able to cleave the backbone is therefore even stronger, i.e. more unlikely to be overcome. This can be seen exemplarily around nt position 80 (SHL 0): this is the position of the nucleosome dyad, i.e. the position where the DNA spans, as a single helix without counterpart, the side of the nucleosome where entry and exit sites are found. As expected, DNase I cleavage is strongly reduced at this site, as the DNA is experiencing the strongest interaction forces here, and is even more inaccessible due to the near-by entry and exit sites.

I assume that the effect of irregular DNase I cleavage can be reduced by optimizing reaction conditions, i.e. changing cleavage times, DNase I concentrations, reaction work-up, etc. Evidence for this is given by published DNase I footprinting traces of NCP-601, which show much more uniform cleavage patterns in the NCP region.^[62] If this succeeds, footprinting of nucleosomal DNA should be possible.

Figure 21: **a) Hydroxyl radical footprint of nucleosomal DNA (Widom 601).** **b) DNase I footprint of nucleosomal DNA (Widom 601).** Electropherograms of labelled DNA (Widom 601 sequence with 6FAM label on 5'-end) reconstituted into nucleosome core particles were produced by capillary electrophoresis with laser-induced fluorescence detection. **a)** Hydroxyl radicals generate a regular pattern of increasing and decreasing amplitude with a periodicity of ~ 10 bp (corresponding to the positions of outward-facing minor grooves), which cannot be evaluated further due to method-specific backdraws. **b)** DNase I cleaves only very few positions, which are very prominent compared to the rest. The prominent positions have a periodicity of roughly 10 bp as well, and occur in the same regions as pronounced hydroxyl radical cleavage.

3.3.3. Assessment of DNA-PyBAPPA interactions by footprinting

3.3.3.1. Hydroxyl radical footprinting complicates interpretation of interactions

The fine cleavage of DNA by hydroxyl radicals due to their extremely small size presented a big advantage for footprinting of NCPs. When footprinting DNA-PyBAPPA interactions, however, this became a major hurdle.

As previously discussed, the continuous signal, i.e. the overlapping of unspecific cleavage products, does not allow to detect the background while recording capillary electrophoresis traces. Therefore, the standard algorithms provided with the *PeakScanner* software failed to recognize correct peak heights and rendered the signal unusable.

This effect might be handled by assuming a constant background and relying on the peak heights only. Setting the signals to reference heights might yield valuable information then.

Furthermore, it might be possible to reduce the overlapping by improvement of the capillary electrophoresis resolution. In our setup, this possibility was not given, as capillary length, voltage, polymer, etc. were fixed by the routines used by our cooperation partner.

The low resolution of unspecific cleavage products is a known problem and one of the main reasons of the popularity of the DNase I approach over hydroxyl radical footprinting. It was therefore chosen to focus on DNase I footprinting next.

3.3.3.2. DNase I footprinting is more easily evaluated for DNA-ligand interactions

When trying to analyze interactions of DNA with small molecules in a quantitative fashion, it is of utmost importance to generate a reproducible, easily evaluable signal. This is only achieved when the baseline is reached between single nucleotides, i.e. low background noise is present. DNase I footprinting presents this advantage.

After optimization, DNase I footprinting was able to generate very clean traces with easily discriminable peaks. However, due to the sequence selectivity of DNase I, these peaks are varying in height very strongly, some being not cleaved at all.

Figure 22: *DNase I footprint of PyBAPPA-DNA interactions (Widom 601). A) Overview. B) Details.* Labelled DNA (Widom 601 sequence with 6FAM label on 5'-end) was cleaved by DNase I in the presence of varying concentrations of PyBAPPA 2. Fragments were analyzed by capillary electrophoresis with laser-induced fluorescence detection. An overview of all found fragments is given in **A**). Details in **B**) show the concentration-dependent reduction of cleavage rates (green to red: increasing PyBAPPA concentrations: control, 10 nM, 100 nM, 1 μ M, 10 μ M). Peaks at nt position 43.8 show no significant change in peak area, indicating no interaction of PyBAPPA with the DNA. To evaluate the cleavage ratios despite different amounts of DNA injected, all traces were corrected with a factor determined by equalizing the peak area at \sim 63.5 nt.

Figure 23: **Reproducibility of concentration-dependent footprinting.** **A–C)** Shown are traces from three biological replicates around nucleotide positions 102–108. The ratio between peak areas is similar between the different replicates, which provides evidence for the reproducibility of the data, as is the similar peak size. **D)** Relative peak areas are presented against the concentration of PyBAPPA for the shown biological replicates at the indicated, rounded nucleotide position. The solid line is a fit of the data points against Clark’s Theorem, and yields the coefficients $K_D' = 11.68 \pm 0.45 \mu\text{M}$ ($R^2 = 0.99$), and $K_D' = 24.38 \pm 2.0 \mu\text{M}$ ($R^2 = 0.94$), for nt position 102.5 and 105.1, respectively. Plots at other nucleotide positions can be found in the Appendix.

When generating concentration-dependent series, however, the varying peak heights are rendered undisturbing by using relative peak areas instead of absolute ones. Until the signal-to-noise ratio prevents reliable measurements, with this approach even a small signal can be followed quantitatively.

Figure 23 shows evidence that DNase I footprinting is able to generate concentration-dependent series of DNA-ligand interaction traces, which behave in a consistent way.

Plotting relative peak areas against the concentration, and fitting data points of three biological replicates against Clark's Theorem for binding, it is possible to determine apparent K_D values (for details cf. the Appendix)¹⁹. As Clark's Theorem is assuming a single interaction sites, the determined K_D values do not equal the real K_D values of the specific equilibrium. Instead, they are giving the apparent K_D' values, neglecting that ligand is removed by interactions with different binding sites, leading to a higher number for the apparent than the real K_D value.

This behavior is indeed found for the K_D' values generated by footprinting the PyBAPPA-DNA interaction (cf. Table 8). Unfortunately, the data density is rather low, as DNase I cleavage produced only one fragment each for two positions of interest (nt -45 – -41, and nt -17 – -13). When evaluating positions with more available fragments (e.g. nt +12 – +17), it became clear that the apparent K_D' values change from peak to peak. Similar behavior is to be expected at nucleotide positions where only one peak was evaluable – it must be kept in mind that this is not necessarily the peak which was influenced strongest by ligand binding, and might therefore lie off the mark significantly.

Considering this, I assume that the observed signal at position 59.8 (subsequence AATTT) is giving only weak evidence of the underlying interaction, and that its K_D' value is too high. The signals at nt positions 85.4, 86.6, and 87.5 (subsequence AAAATT) indicate an interaction with focus on nt position 87.5 (K_D' values decrease in this direction). Comparing this value to nt position 26.0 (AATT), the relations in interaction strength are represented correctly. Subsequence ATTA (nt position 102.5 and 105.1) can therefore be predicted to be weaker than AATT ($K_D = 1.0 \pm 0.2 \mu\text{M}$).

¹⁹ It should be noted here, that the method measures IC_{50} , but I assume that $K_D = IC_{50}$ because the DNA concentrations are negligible (20 nM).

Table 8: *Found apparent dissociation constants (K_D') vs. separately determined real dissociation constants (K_D). Data for K_D from Sánchez et al.^[19] K_D' was determined by fitting relative peak heights from concentration-dependent series of DNase I footprinting against Clark's Theorem.*

nt position (CE)	Assumed position in Chua notation	DNA subsequence	$K_D' / \mu\text{M}$	$K_D / \mu\text{M}$
26.0	-45 – -41	AATT	6.63 ± 0.4	1.0 ± 0.2
59.8	-17 – -13	AATTT	38.6 ± 4.9	0.334 ± 40
85.4	+12 – +17	AAAATT	10.3 ± 1.2	? #
86.6			8.59 ± 1.6	
87.5			4.64 ± 0.9	
102.5	+29 – +32	ATTA	11.6 ± 0.37	?
105.1			24.7 ± 1.5	

#: Although the K_D value for this specific subsequence is not known, it might be comparable to the K_D values of the following related subsequences: $K_D(\text{AATTT}) = 0.334 \pm 0.040 \mu\text{M}$, $K_D(\text{AAATTT}) = 0.229 \pm 0.063 \mu\text{M}$.

3.3.4. Summary

In the preceding chapter, I described how I developed a method to measure interactions between linear or nucleosomal DNA and small molecules or histone proteins, respectively. Capillary electrophoresis with laser-induced fluorescence detection (CE-LIF) was, to the best of my knowledge, not applied to footprinting of small molecules before, and presents major advantages over traditional footprinting. I discussed the pitfalls of CE-LIF footprinting and gave suggestions how to improve the method in further work.

Footprinting nucleosomal DNA with hydroxyl radical cleavage allowed me to visualize the DNA-histone interaction. DNase I footprinting did not produce the desired results yet, which put footprinting of the interaction of small molecules with nucleosomal DNA out of reach for the time being.

DNase I footprinting of linear DNA analyzed by CE-LIF showed, for the first time, interactions between a small molecule and DNA. I presented evidence for the reproducibility of this newly developed method, and calculated apparent K_D' values.

The determined K_D' values seem to be a good indicator for interaction strength, as can be seen from an exemplarily generated data set for the interaction of PyBAPPA with Widom 601 DNA. All expected interactions were found. Furthermore, at nucleotide positions where no interactions were expected (e.g. in $(G/C)_n$ tracts), none were evident from the data, serving as a negative control.

4. Conclusion & Outlook

In this chapter, I want to conclude my work, and give an outlook on future work towards a multivalent nucleosome sensor.

The results generated with *AutoDock Vina* allowed me to correlate the computational model with experimentally determined affinities with a high goodness-of-fit inside a class of receptor and ligand. It was possible to predict the ranks of different receptors to a certain ligand mostly correctly, but ranks between different ligands did not reflect the experimentally determined affinities.

The newly developed *groover-szybki* approach allowed me to evaluate favorable interaction sites of the capped PyBAPPA fragment with nucleosomal Widom 601 DNA *in silico*. As no experimental data exists on this question, the predictions derived from my model will allow us to push the development of a multivalent nucleosome sensor further.

DNase I footprinting of linear Widom 601 DNA gave us an impression of the interaction between PyBAPPA and the Widom 601 sequence, and is a first step towards knowledge of the interactions between PyBAPPA binder moieties and NCP-601. It is in this regard analogously useful for us, as is crystallographic fragment screening in drug design.

With the presented *in silico* approaches, it should be possible to evaluate all possible nucleotide combinations to expand our knowledge on the interaction of BAPPA derivatives with specific DNA nucleotides. Augmented with molecular dynamics simulations, this would allow us to understand the sequence-selectivity and interaction mechanism of BAPPA derivatives in finer detail.

Footprinting with DNase I or hydroxyl radicals is a key method for the prediction of interactions between binder moieties of a multivalent nucleosome sensor with NCP-601. Optimizing the reaction conditions and data evaluation procedures further, we will be able to generate a map of favorable interaction sites, allowing us to improve the design of our sensor in a rational way.

Evidence for affinity of PyBAPPA to a previously untested subsequence (ATTA) has to be confirmed or falsified by determination of the K_D value by other methods.

Further, it should be possible to footprint also ligands with different interaction mechanisms, e.g. intercalators or major groove binders. This will allow us to increase the diversity of the library employed to identify a nucleosome sensor.

5. Experimental part

5.1. Plasmid amplification

Plasmid pGEM-3z/601 was a generous gift from Karim Bouazoune (Addgene plasmid # 26656, deposited by Jonathan Widom).

To facilitate long-term storage and sequencing, the plasmid was replicated in DH5 alpha cells.

Therefore, the plasmid was diluted from 1.1 µg/µL to a final concentration of 0.1 µg/µL. Of this, 0.5 µL plasmid dilution (containing 50 ng plasmid) was added to 50 µL of competent cells (*E. coli* DH5 alpha). The cells were transformed by addition to electroporation cuvettes with 2 mm gap, and a 5.8 ms pulse with 2.5 kV was applied. 1 mL of LB medium (10 g/L tryptone, 5 g/L yeast extract, 10 g/L NaCl) was added to the cells immediately, and the cells were recovered while shaking at 37°C and 800 rpm for 1 h.

Cells were plated onto agar containing ampicillin, and grown over night at 37°C. A streak of bacteria was transferred into 5 mL of LB medium containing ampicillin, and grown for 24 h at 37°C and 200 rpm.

For long-term storage, 300 µL glycerol (80%) was added to 700 µL of the bacterial culture, mixed and shock-frozen in liquid nitrogen, after which the glycerol stock was stored at -80°C.

The plasmid was prepared from 4 mL of bacterial culture with a Sigma GenElute HP Plasmid Miniprep Kit by following the manufacturer's instructions. Eluted in 50 µL millipore water, this resulted in a plasmid concentration of 331 ng/µL as determined by NanoDrop measurement.

5.2. Agarose gel electrophoresis

To analyze DNA products, gel electrophoresis was performed in 2% agarose gels. Therefore, to millipore water 2% (w/v) of agarose were added and heated to boiling in a microwave oven. After the solution cleared from particles and streaks, it was poured into forms and a comb inserted into the hot solution.

After solidification, the comb was carefully removed and the agarose gel placed in an electrophoresis chamber and covered with TAE buffer (40 mM Tris, 1 mM EDTA, 20 mM acetic acid).

Samples were mixed with loading buffer (NEB Gel Loading Dye Buffer) and pipetted into the wells. A size standard (NEB Quick-Load Purple 100bp DNA Ladder) was added in a separate well.

Gels were run at 6–8 V/cm (electrode distance: 15 cm) for approximately 40 min.

5.3. Native Polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis

To analyze molecular weights of DNA or NCP, native polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (native PAGE) was performed.

Polyacrylamide gels were poured as 5% gels in 0.5xTBE (10 mM Tris, 45 mM borate, 1 mM EDTA). Therefore, 40% acrylamide solution (37.5 : 1, acrylamide : bisacrylamide) was diluted in 0.5xTBE. Reaction was started by addition of 0.005 volumes of an APS solution (20% in water) and 0.0005 volumes TEMED.

Pouring the mixture immediately into commercially available gel cassettes, a comb was inserted. After complete polymerization (approximately 40 min), the comb was removed and the cassette placed into an electrophoresis chamber filled with 0.5xTBE.

The wells were flushed with the running buffer by pipette or syringe, and one well loaded with sample dye containing xylene cyanol, bromophenol blue and orange gelb. The gel was pre-run at 90 V until orange gelb left the gel (approximately 40 min).

After adding roughly 0.1 volumes glycerol or PEG-6000 to the samples, varying volumes in the range of 3-10 μ L were loaded into the wells.

The gel was run at 90 V, \sim 5mA, for 40 min.

5.4. Gel evaluation with Chemidoc and ImageLab

DNA bands in the gels were visualized depending on the type of DNA.

Fluorescent DNA was detected directly by label detection with Chemidoc instruments, choosing parameters suitable for fluorescein detection.

Gels containing unlabelled DNA were post-stained by allowing the gel to float in millipore water containing 1 μ g ethidium bromide per 50 mL water, or 10 μ L Midori Green per 30 mL water. The bands were visualized by detection of ethidium bromide with Chemidoc instruments.

Quantitation of the gel bands was performed densitometrically with ImageLab (BioRad). Therefore, lanes were identified on the gel picture, bands picked, and background automatically subtracted. The so-generated lane profiles were inspected for the band areas and heights and compared with each other or marker lanes, respectively.

5.5. Determination of DNA concentration

DNA concentrations were determined by measuring the absorption at 230, 260, and 280 nm, respectively of 1 μ L of sample on a NanoDrop instrument (NanoDrop 2200, or NanoDrop 2200c).

The absorption values were corrected against the corresponding buffer solution.

The corrected absorption value was converted into DNA concentrations by using a conversion factor of 50 ng/ μ L / OD₂₆₀ (10 mm).

5.6. PCR

Polymerase chain reaction of the Widom 601 substrate was performed by use of the pGEM-3z/601 plasmid and the following oligonucleotides (purchased from Sigma Genosys):

Name	Sequence (5' → 3')	Application
[6FAM]601_F	[6FAM]CCTGGAGAATCCCGGTGC	Forward primer for amplification of 147 bp Widom 601 sequence, labelled at 5'-end with fluorescein moiety
601_R	CAGGATGTATATATCTGACACGTGCC	Reverse primer for amplification of 147 bp Widom 601 sequence

5.6.1. PCR for end-labelling

For selective end-labelling, a fluorescently labelled primer was used. The reaction mixture contained 0.5 μ M forward primer, 0.5 μ M reverse primer, plasmid DNA (final concentration 1 ng/ μ L), ddNTPs (200 μ M each), 3% DMSO, and Phusion polymerase (1 U / 50 μ L PCR volume) in the proprietary HF buffer.

PCR reaction was performed in an Eppendorf Thermocycler, according to the following program: initial denaturation at 98°C for 30s; 30 cycles of: denaturation: 98°C, 8s, annealing: 60°C, 20s, elongation: 72°C, 10s; final elongation at 72°C for 4min ; hold at 4°C until the PCR product was purified.

5.6.2. Purification of PCR products

PCR products were purified by column purification with QIAquick spin columns or Qiagen MinElute prep kits according to the manufacturer's protocol. Elution was performed with millipore water or elution buffer (10 mM Tris-HCl pH 8.0, 1mM EDTA) of the required volume.

5.7. Reconstitution of NCPs

NCPs were reconstituted by the salt-dialysis method.

A final concentration of 100-200 ng DNA per μL reaction volume was chosen. The DNA was brought into 1xSDB (“salt dialysis buffer”: 10 mM Tris, 1 mM EDTA, 2 M NaCl, 1 mM β -mercaptoethanol), and mixed with HeLa histones. The amount of HeLa histones necessary to reconstitute the DNA into NCPs was determined experimentally.

Portions of 50 μL were given into dialysis cells (molecular weight cut-off: 5,000–8,000 kDa), and allowed to float in 1xSDB for 1h. The NaCl concentration was step-wise reduced (2 M \rightarrow 1 M \rightarrow 500 mM \rightarrow 50 mM; dialysis time 1h each), while keeping the other buffer components constant.

Purity of the reconstituted NCPs was checked by native PAGE, and found to be > 90%.

5.8. Footprinting experiments

5.8.1. Experimental procedure for DNase I footprinting

To generate DNase I footprints, a DNase I stock (3.2 U/ μL , 10 mM Tris, pH 7.5, 10 mM MgCl_2 , 17 mM CaCl_2 , 50% glycerol) was diluted in reaction buffer (10 mM Tris-HCl, pH 7.5, 50 mM NaCl, 2.5 mM MgCl_2 , 0.5 mM CaCl_2) to a concentration of 0.3 mU / μL .

Of this stock, 1.5 mU (equals 5 μL DNase I dilution; final concentration: 0.3 mU/ μL , equal to 3 mU DNase I per μg DNA) was added rapidly to 45 μL of a premixed mixture containing 100 ng (final concentration 20 nM) fluorescently labelled DNA, 10 mM Tris-HCl, pH 7.5, 50 mM NaCl, 2.5 mM MgCl_2 , 0.5 mM CaCl_2 , and varying concentrations of PyBAPPA (0 M, 10 nM, 100 nM, 1 μM , 10 μM ; provided by Benedikt Heinrich).

After exactly 2 min, the reaction was stopped by addition of 5 μL stop solution (10 mM Tris-HCl, pH 7.5, 50 mM EDTA), leading to complexation of Mg^{2+} and Ca^{2+} (final EDTA concentration: 9 mM, divalent cations: < 3mM), which are crucial for DNase I function.

By addition of 6 μL NaOAc (3 M), mixing, addition of 180 μL ethanol (100%, -20°C), and keeping the mixture at -80°C for 30 min, DNA precipitation was performed. The DNA was pelleted by centrifugation at 14 000 rpm, 4°C , for 20 min, and the supernatant removed by careful pipetting.

The pellet was dried completely by lyophilizing (i.e. freeze-drying and application of reduced pressure) for 5 min, and resuspended in 10 μL millipore water.

Concentration of the DNA was determined by NanoDrop, and a sample volume equaling 5–10 ng of DNA dissolved in a mixture of 12 μL formamide and 0.5 μL size standard BTO-550.

The samples were subjected to capillary electrophoresis by electrokinetic injection for 5s (unless otherwise stated) at 15 kV, and run at 15 kV, 60°C, for 28 min over a capillary of 36 cm filled with POP-4 polymer (Applied Biosystems).

5.8.2. Experimental procedure for hydroxyl radical footprinting

Hydroxyl radical footprinting was performed by addition of 7 μL of a freshly mixed solution of sodium ascorbate (final concentration: 0.2 mM), Fe^{2+} and EDTA (0.04 mM, and 0.08 mM, respectively; from $\text{Fe}(\text{NH}_4)_2(\text{SO}_4)_2 \times 6 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ solution containing EDTA), and H_2O_2 (0.03%) to 43 μL of an equilibrated DNA solution (containing at final concentrations: 20 nM DNA, 10 mM Tris, 50 mM NaCl, varying concentrations of PyBAPPA).

Reaction was stopped by addition of 10 μL DMSO, and DNA preparation performed as for DNase I footprinting. Analysis of the fragments was carried out by capillary electrophoresis.

5.8.3. Capillary electrophoresis with laser-induced fluorescence detection

The prepared samples were run on an ABI PRISM 310 Genetic analyzer, provided by our cooperation partner Dr. Cornelia Brendell, operated by Lisa Koch. Separation inside the capillary was achieved by using the free-flowing polymer POP-4, using the conditions indicated above.

Traces were evaluated with the *PeakScanner* software.^[63] Data was analyzed with default settings, and peak sizes called by loading the appropriate size standard fragment lengths. As the smallest documented size standard fragment was at 60 bp, a non-documented but reproducible impurity peak was used. This impurity peak was arbitrarily set to 16 bp.

For DNase I samples, calibration of peak heights was performed by choosing a prominent peak at ~ 63.5 bp as standard. It was set to an arbitrary height, and the heights of peaks from other samples were corrected accordingly by evaluating the ratio between peak heights at ~ 63.5 bp.

Peak heights were expressed relative to the reference trace (0 M) of a concentration series, and fitted to Clark's Receptor Theory to calculate K_D values.

5.9. Computational methods

All calculations were performed on Debian Linux workstations with an Intel Core i5 CPU and 4 GB of memory.

For visualization, RMSD determination, and protonation of PDB structures, *chimera*^[64] was used.

DNA modelling was done by *MOE 2014.09*,^[65] or *Web 3DNA*.^[66]

Energy optimization was performed with *szybki*^[47] for Cartesian coordinates of all small molecule atoms, employing exact van-der-Waals values and a Poisson-Boltzmann solvent model.

For data extraction various self-written python or bash scripts were used.

Data visualization was achieved with *R 3.1.1*.^[67]

5.10. Molecules used for in silico experiments

A series of molecules were represented in silico to include them into modelling exercises.

PheBAPPA was extracted from the corresponding NMR structures (unpublished).

For the generation of PyBAPPA, the central phenyl carbon atom was manually changed to a nitrogen atom in the PDB formatted file, and the corresponding hydrogen removed.

All molecules were represented in PDB formatted files, which contained the coordinates of all atoms, as well as their atomic type and internal numbering.

NCP-601 was represented by the deposited PDB structure 3lz1.

5.11. Traditional docking (AutoDock)

Traditional docking, i.e. docking of a fully flexible ligand to a rigid receptor, was done by using *AutoDock Vina 1.1.2*.^[44] Molecules for docking were prepared by *AutoDockTools*. The docking box was centered on the geometrical center of the respective DNA fragment, and had a volume of 30x30x30 Å (which included most of the DNA). Docking was performed using the default settings of *AutoDock Vina*.

5.12. Simplified docking

Simplified docking was performed by a protocol supplemented by knowledge-based assumptions about the ligand's binding mode.

5.12.1. Description of self-written tools: groover

To facilitate the extraction and re-generation of the ligand's supposed binding mode, a program was developed to extract the ligand and re-generate its binding mode at different positions in the DNA minor groove: *groover*.

For generation of initial poses, the binding mode of PheBAPPA was regenerated at every position in the minor groove of the nucleosomal DNA with *groover*. This was done by creating helix and minor groove as described below, and positioning the ligand to accordingly selected combinations of dummy atoms. Success of the alignment was checked by evaluating the RMSD values between dummies of the ligand and target, which was consistently below 2 Å.

To generate the helix and minor groove axis, I employed an approach similar to El Hassan and Calladine, whose seminal appendix on the calculation of major- and minor-groove widths set standards.^[69]

Helix axis dummies (H_i) were generated by constructing point $H_i = 0.5*(P_i+p_i)$, i.e. by constructing the mid-point of phosphates of base-pairing nucleotides (whereas P_i notifies the vector of the reference strand phosphate). Minor groove dummies (M_i) were constructed using an offset of $m=-2$ to minimize discrepancies between indexed and actual position, by calculating $M_i = 0.5*(P_i + p_{i-2})$ at position i . The whole set of chosen alignment dummies for a placement on position i consists of: H_{i-1} , H_i , M_{i-1} , M_{i+3} .

Fine-graining of the grid points was achieved by linear combination of base-pair step dummy atoms with $H_{i+a} = a*H_{i+1} + (1-a)*H_i$ and $M_{i+a} = a*M_{i+1} + (1-a)*M_i$, respectively.

The resulting points can be seen in Figure 24.

Figure 24: Structure of helix and minor groove descriptor dummy atoms. A) For orientation, a representation of pdb id 3lz1 is given. B) Helix descriptor dummy atoms are resulting in a dense series of points, matching the helical axis spline. C) Minor groove dummy atoms follow the spline of the minor groove, rotating around the helical axis. Helix and minor groove dummies were generated by groover and used to regenerate the known binding mode of PheBAPPA at every position in the nucleosomal DNA minor groove.

Extraction of the ligand

The extraction step, i.e. separating the ligand from its reference structure but conserving the binding mode, was done with the following algorithm (in pseudocode):

```
what receptor? → Dickerson DNA (from NMR structure)
what ligand? → PheBAPPA (from NMR structure)
construct helix_dummies(Dickerson DNA)
construct minor_groove_dummies(Dickerson DNA)
at which position is the ligand roughly placed? → i
select helix_dummies(i), ... minor_groove_dummies(i) → dummies_receptor
merge dummies_receptor and ligand → output
```

The output consisted therefore of a pdb file, containing the Cartesian coordinates of the ligand as well as of four dummy atoms, which were declared as such. This file was used for the further steps.

Ligand placement

The extracted ligand was placed into DNA minor groove by aligning the previously described dummy atoms of helix and groove axis from the ligand construct and the DNA molecule, processed by *groover*, respectively. Success of alignments was evaluated by low RMSD values. The ligand transitioned smoothly through the minor groove, as inspected visually from the generated structures.

To generate a denser search space, the grid points were fine-grained with distances that corresponded to 1/10 of the distance between base-pair steps of dummy atoms, i.e. ~ 0.5 Å.

The placement step, i.e. loading the extracted ligand and aligning it to a new target, is described by the following pseudocode (for clarity, the actual names are used instead of abstract variables):

```
what target? → 3lz1
what ligand? → extracted PheBAPPA
```

```
construct helix_dummies(3lz1)
construct minor_groove_dummies(3lz1)
to which position at target? → i
select helix_dummies(i), ... minor_groove_dummies(i) → dummies_target
select dummy_atoms(PheBAPPA) → dummies_ligand
align dummies_ligand to dummies_target
store alignment_translation_and_rotation
delete dummy_atoms(PheBAPPA)
apply alignment_translation_and_rotation to PheBAPPA → output
```

The output consists therefore of a pdb file containing the ligand in its original binding mode, but at different Cartesian coordinates and with another orientation. It was fitted to the shape of the minor groove of the target receptor, in this example the minor groove of NCP-601 (PDB ID: 3lz1).

Mapping to nucleotide positions

For data visualization, the ligand positions were mapped to the nucleotide to which the phosphate with the smallest distance between central atom of the ligand and phosphate atom belonged. A description of this procedure is given in the Appendix.

5.12.2. Energy optimization with *szybki*

The output files from groover were used as input files to a subsequent step of energy optimization, performed with *szybki* 1.8.0.2.^[47]

If not otherwise specified, flags of *szybki* were set for exact calculation of van-der-Waals interactions (-exact_vdw), treatment of electrostatic interactions according to Poisson-Boltzmann theory (-prot_elec PB) and optimization of all atoms' coordinates (-optGeometry cart).

Energy values were derived from *szybki*'s log output for successful.

5.12.3. Description of self-written tool: ruler

To facilitate the evaluation of data generated by the fragment docking via the *groover-szybki* approach, a tool for automated data extraction and calculation was developed: *ruler*.

Ruler is a program to identify atoms by a chemoinformatic description and allows actions to take place between those atoms, e.g. distance measurement or creation of a chemical bond.

Identification of the atoms was based on the SMILES string interpretation function of the openbabel suite.^[70] Terminal C_ω carbon atoms in the linker moiety were recognized by the SMILES string “[CH3]~C~C”, whereas the terminal C_Ω atom of a binder moiety was recognized by the SMILES string “CC(=O)NC=N”.

The following pseudocode describes the underlying algorithm:

```
loop through all molecule combinations:
load molecule1
load molecule2
find atom(molecule1, smiles_string) → store target_atom1
find atom(molecule2, smiles_string) → store target_atom2
measure_distance(target_atom1, target_atom2) → output
start loop with next pair
```

5.12.4. Generation of multivalency data set with ruler

To generate the matrix of all possible binder combinations, the distance between the two intramolecular C_ω (for linker moieties) or the intermolecular C_Ω of a given combination of poses (for binder moieties) was measured with *ruler*, and in case of the binder moieties stored together with the sum of total energies of the corresponding poses.

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7. Appendix

7.1. “Scheme 4”, and how to number a NCP

The unambiguously description of NCPs is a troublesome task. The early crystal structures contained a palindromic DNA, which, in combination with the histone pairs in the middle, formed a pseudo-dyad symmetry. Numbering of the super-helix locations (SHL) did not have to identify between “left” and “right”, but could refer to both sides at the same time. It did so by naming the SHL for example ± 0.5 , etc.

The DNA sequence was therefore also numbered from -72 at the respective 5'-end to +72 at the 3'-ends. This led to base pair “0” at the dyad axis, and base pairs were having the same index with different sign.

However, with the advent of non-palindromic DNA, the Widom 601 sequence, there was a “left” and “right”, a beginning and an end. Notation, however, adopted only slowly. The paper describing the NCP-601 crystal structure,^[6] still used the ambiguous plus-minus notation. This was partially, because both orientations were identified within the crystal structures.

When I try to name interaction sites, these have to be unambiguously and comprehensible for the reader. Throughout the whole document, I focused therefore on pdb structure “3LZ1”, and made the strand “J” of the pdb file my reference strand. This is in accordance with the visualization by Chua et al., who aligned all known strong positioning sequences and set a referencing standard (cf. Figure 1 in the reference).^[41]

I attached my numbering scheme, giving the Chua notation on top of my reference strand. To implement “backwards-compatibility”, I included as well the notation used in the original NCP-601 paper, which is the same for the 0 – +72 bp position of strand “J”, but is numbering the nucleotides of strand “I” exactly the other way around.

Unfortunately, I had to employ a second numbering scheme as well. The footprinting process did not allow to set nucleotide sizes to the negative, so I had to relocate bp -72 of strand “J” to +1. However, I think that this offset of +73 bp is easily manageable, especially with the numbering scheme in hand.

7.2. Mapping the minor groove

When focusing on DNA minor groove binding, the understanding of nucleotides participating in constructing the minor groove is of utmost importance.

However, as there is no agreed definition of how to reference DNA minor grooves, it is sometimes unclear how the nucleotides are positioned absolutely in the NCP.

Vasudevan et al.^[6] chose to mark base-pairs which they define as being part of inward-facing minor grooves. In my opinion, there are nucleotides marked as inward-facing, which clearly are not. I am especially concerned about the fact that they mark base-pairs and define, that they form a minor groove. When constructing truly orthogonal minor grooves like I do in this work, base-pairing is not anymore a matter for the composition of the minor groove.

I want to show this on an example. We shall take the “Dickerson DNA” (pdb: 1bna; note that the Dickerson DNA is numbered on one strand A1–A12, and on the other B13–24. A12 is base-pairing with B13, and B24 with A1.) and construct a two-dimensional scheme of it (compare for this issue the seminal paper by El Hassan & Calladine,^[69] and see Figure A1).

As you see, the nucleotide backbone is bend. Wanting to define the minor groove, in my eyes it seems sensible to find the shortest, i.e. orthogonal connection, between the backbones and define them as aligning the minor groove, constructing in a way a triangle between the “rails” of the phosphate backbone and the floor of the minor groove. This is exactly what El Hassan & Calladine do, too.

Trying to construct the shortest distance between phosphates of opposite backbones, one can clearly see a trend towards shorter distance with phosphates that are not base-paired, but (depending on the DNA substrate) 2–4 base-pairs away. El Hassan & Calladine call this the “offset” **m** of nucleotides in the minor groove (in Figure A1: the reference nucleotide is “i”, on the opposite strand: $j=i+m$; alternatively, the names are given in the notation found in the PDB).

Therefore, when trying to indicate minor (or major) grooves in DNA sequences, the offset must be considered always.

Figure A1: *Crystal structure and planar visualization of the Dickerson DNA minor groove. Distances between a reference phosphate (“A8”) and different phosphates of the complementary DNA strand. The shortest distance is not found between phosphates of the base-pair (A8/B18), but to phosphates of up to 4 nucleotides away.*

In my work, I used a second method to clarify the position of ligands in the minor groove. I mapped their center, or at least a clearly defined atom, to the nearest phosphate of my reference strand. An example for this is seen in Figure A2.

From this, we can also derive another measure, the “stretch” of the ligand: this is the index difference of phosphate groups from the one nearest to the central phenyl carbon of PheBAPPA, to the phosphates which are nearest to the amidinium moieties. Depending on the concrete groove bend, this is approximately 2 nucleotides to each side, resulting in a stretch of approximately 4–5 nucleotides (or, more correctly: phosphates) covered by one BAPPA derivative molecule.

Figure A2: NMR structure PheBAPPA in the Dickerson DNA minor groove. Distances between the central phenyl carbon and different phosphates of the reference DNA strand are shown. The shortest distance is found to the phosphate of base A8, allowing to map the ligand in an unambiguous way.

7.3. Chemical structures of pentamidine, propamidine, and BAPPA

In the Introduction I shortly introduced pentamidine, and its derivative propamidine. From this the BAPPA moiety is inspired. Here I want to highlight the relationship between their chemical structures.

Scheme A1: *Chemical structures of BAPPA (6), propamidine (7) and pentamidine (8). It becomes clear that BAPPA is the aza-derivative of propamidine, which is related to propamidine, but differs in two methylene bridges.*

7.4. Clark's receptor theory, and how to calculate K_D '

Thorough introductions to general ligand binding assays,^[71] tailored to footprinting fitting,^[53] and a practical approach,^[72] are available. Here, I only want to give a short overview of the concrete formulas employed.

Clark's Theorem is a theory about the process of receptor-ligand interaction. It assumes that the following holds true:

- “1. The interaction is reversible; the association reaction is bimolecular while the dissociation is uni- molecular.
2. All the receptor molecules are equivalent and independent
3. The biological response is proportional to the number of occupied receptor sites.
4. The interaction and response are measured after the reaction has reached equilibrium.
5. The active chemical agent does not undergo degradation or participate in other reactions, and only exists in either a free (unbound) form or bound to the receptor. “^[72]

Under those assumptions, Clark's Theorem says:

$$B = \frac{(L_T + K_D + R_T) - \sqrt{(-L_T - K_D - R_T)^2 - 4 R_T L_T}}{2}$$

where B is the bound ligand concentration (which equals the concentration of formed complex, sometimes referred as [RL]), L_T the total ligand concentration, K_D the dissociation constant, and R_T the total receptor concentration.

Normalizing this into the ratio of receptor bound, and therefore signal created (bound receptor means ligand present, which means: footprint = signal visible), it is:

$$\text{signal} = 1 - \frac{(L_T + K_D + R_T) - \sqrt{(-L_T - K_D - R_T)^2 - 4 R_T L_T}}{2 R_T} \quad (\text{eq. 1})$$

With this formula, I assume, that without ligand present, the maximum possible cleavage (=100%) is reached. Under saturating conditions, it should be possible to reach 0% cleavage. (Note that Hampshire et al. describe that they seldomly see saturating conditions at 0% cleavage, but allow for a residual term. This approach is not followed here.)

Therefore, I manually extract the peak area in the control trace **ref** (containing no ligand), normalize it to 1, and set every other trace **i** into relationship to the control peak:

$$\text{signal}(i) = \frac{A_i}{A_{\text{ref}}}$$

These points are plotted against the total ligand concentration used in this assay, and all available data points are fitted to equation 1 by employing R's function *nls* for non-linear regression. This yields the coefficient K_D' .

Actually, we determine with this method IC_{50} , not directly K_D . However, IC_{50} can be described as:

$$IC_{50} = K_D + R_T/2$$

As the receptor concentration was low (20 nM of DNA), I had to accept an error in the order of magnitude of 10 nM.

Further references

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7.5. Further footprint fits

In the following, all generated K_D ' plots are presented. As the procedure was still heavily manually based, not all peaks could be evaluated, but only the visually promising ones.

Selbstständigkeitserklärung

Hiermit erkläre ich, dass ich meine Arbeit zur Erlangung des Grades Master of Science gemäß §23 Absatz 7 der Prüfungsordnung für den Studiengang „Chemie“ mit dem Abschluss „Master of Science (M.Sc.)“ der Philipps-Universität Marburg vom 15. Februar 2012 mit dem Titel

„Computer-aided design and experimental evaluation of a novel nucleosome binder“

selbstständig verfasst und keine anderen als die angegebenen Quellen und Hilfsmittel benutzt habe.

Marburg, den 12.02.2016

Robert Giessmann

Veröffentlichungserlaubnis

Die vorliegende Arbeit darf von der Universitätsbibliothek Marburg nach Ablauf einer Sperrfrist von 1 Jahr, d.h. ab dem 12.02.2017, veröffentlicht werden.

Robert Giessmann

Olalla Vázquez

